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The theory of distributions in teaching electrostatics: Multipoles, forces, and boundary conditions

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E-mail: maugv@ciencias.unam.mx**Keywords:** electrostatics, theory of distributions, multipole expansion, boundary conditions, physics education, university teaching

Abstract

This paper presents a way of teaching the standard curriculum of upper-undergraduate electrostatics, the electrostatic potential, the multipole expansion, and the boundary conditions at material interfaces, organized around the theory of distributions. Our aim is practical rather than foundational. In standard treatments the student meets a different technique for each situation, with singular objects introduced informally, multipole terms named but not constructed, and boundary conditions derived by geometric arguments that violate the hypotheses of the theorems they invoke. The difficulties this produces are as much mathematical as physical. We show how a single distributional procedure replaces that patchwork, so that each manipulation the standard course asks the student to accept on the authority of the textbook becomes a result they can derive. We also report on six semesters of classroom experience teaching the material this way in an Electromagnetism II course, including the diagnostic discussions through which students come to question arguments they had previously accepted. The framework also yields results we did not encounter in our review of the literature, namely an explicit charge representation of the 2^n -pole point distribution, a physical interpretation of the dipole and quadrupole moments in terms of centers of charge and moments of inertia, and closed-form expressions for the force and torque on multipoles of arbitrary order.

1 Introduction

Usually, electrostatics is the first encounter with electromagnetic theory for physics students. At the lower undergraduate level, many electrostatics phenomena are explained phenomenologically, with the principal effort placed on developing physical intuition, as in references [1–3]. At the upper undergraduate or graduate level, the emphasis shifts towards a more rigorous formulation in which Maxwell's equations are taken as axioms [4], and the mathematics required to handle the resulting phenomena becomes correspondingly more demanding [5–8]. At our institution this distinction is reflected in the structure of the course, which is divided in two parts. Electromagnetism I, in the fourth semester, follows the phenomenological approach, while Electromagnetism II places mathematical rigour at the centre. The present work proposes a different way of teaching electrostatics at this upper level, suitable for advanced undergraduate and graduate students.

As noted by Jentschura [8], electromagnetism has a reputation for being particularly hard. In our experience, this difficulty is not only related to the physical phenomena under study, but is heavily compounded by the incomplete mathematical framework employed in standard treatments. For instance, singular objects such as point charges are introduced informally, boundary conditions are derived through geometric arguments that quietly violate the assumptions of the theorems they invoke [9], and multipole distributions are constructed through limiting processes whose rigorous justification is never provided [5, 6, 10]. Several standard references acknowledge this informality [1, 5, 6], yet acknowledgement is not resolution. Because these techniques are correct in their results but heterogeneous in their justification, students learn them one by one, with no unifying principle, and must permanently devote part of their attention to remembering which technique applies in

each situation, without a clear understanding of why the manipulations that produced the results are valid. Eventually, the pattern is reproduced as each generation of physicists trains the next.

A central tool at this level is the Dirac delta, used to represent the point charge $q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0)$. In standard references, δ is introduced through the integral property [5, 6, 11]

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{\mathbf{x}' \in \mathbb{R}^3} f(\mathbf{x}') \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}') d^3\mathbf{x}', \quad (1)$$

which in references such as [6] is called *the filtering property*. This expression is sometimes supplemented by the informal prescription [1, 6]

$$\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}') = \begin{cases} \infty & \text{if } \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}', \\ 0 & \text{elsewhere.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Although Eq. (2) is claimed in [6] to be compatible with Eq. (1), an elementary analysis shows their inconsistency. An undergraduate student knows that under Riemann integration δ admits no upper sums, and a more mathematically mature student knows that under Lebesgue integration the object described by Eq. (2) is zero almost everywhere [12]. This is, in our experience, one of the first places where the standard treatment undermines student learning. The student accepts the Dirac delta as a given without ever questioning what it is, and every later manipulation that rests on it is accepted in the same way, since there is no firm ground from which to question it. The difficulty does not stay contained, but cascades through every result built on the delta. Distribution theory [13] resolves this inconsistency by providing the unifying principle that the curriculum is missing. It is the natural language for the point charge and, by extension, for every singular object that appears in electrostatics. A single procedure replaces the heterogeneous techniques and, in our experience as instructors, allows students to attend to the physical content of problems rather than to the selection of mathematical tricks.

References [9, 14, 15] treat electromagnetic phenomena within the distributional framework, but these works are aimed at advanced electrodynamics and are not designed as pedagogical treatments of electrostatics. To the best of our knowledge, the present work is the first systematic attempt to build the standard curriculum of electrostatics on the foundation of distribution theory, with explicit attention to the physical interpretation of every result.

This paper is written for the physics instructor considering whether to incorporate this framework into an upper-undergraduate or graduate Electromagnetism course, rather than for the specialist already fluent in distribution theory. For this reason the derivations of standard results retain the explicit intermediate steps where these illustrate the framework in action, while the technical proofs and longer calculations are deferred to Supplementary Material A.

We have taught this material for six semesters at our institution, and the approach is not simply to present the distributional derivations in place of the standard ones. We use the framework as a diagnostic tool, leading students to re-examine results they had already accepted and to discover for themselves where the standard arguments break down. Specific recommendations for classroom implementation, together with the diagnostic discussions that anchor this practice, are given in Section 6. A consolidated map of the points at which the standard treatment is criticized in this paper, with the section where each is resolved, is given in Table 1.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the minimal distributional machinery used in the body of the paper. Section 3 derives the electrostatic potential for charge distributions of arbitrary support directly from Maxwell's equations. Section 4 develops the multipole expansion, derives the force and torque on 2^n -poles, and shows how extended charge distributions reduce to their point-multipole equivalents through the physical interpretation of the moments. Section 5 derives the boundary conditions at dielectric–dielectric and dielectric–conductor interfaces from the distributional Poisson equation. Section 6 discusses classroom implementation.

Table 1: Consolidated map of the specific points at which the standard treatment of electrostatics is criticized in this paper, with the section where each point is resolved. References in the third column are those cited at the corresponding location in the paper. Among the textbook references, Griffiths [1], Jackson [5], and Zangwill [6] are the principal standard references for Electromagnetism II in the program at our institution.

Specific point	Issue in the standard treatment	Resolved in
<i>Foundational: the Dirac delta and singular charge distributions</i>		
The defining property of δ	Defined by the integral property (1) [5, 6, 11] together with the informal description (2) [1, 6], which is inconsistent under Riemann or Lebesgue integration.	Sec. 2
Dimensional consistency of Gauss's law	ρ is used to represent volumetric, surface, line, and point distributions without recognizing that, as a function, it is dimensionally inconsistent in non-volumetric cases [1, 5, 6].	Sec. 3
Derivation of the electrostatic potential	Coulomb's law is taken as the experimental starting point and the potential is built up by extension of a discrete sum to a continuum, without derivation from Maxwell's equations [1–3, 5, 10].	Sec. 3
The Green function and its physical meaning	The Green function and its role as the electrostatic potential of a point charge are frequently absent or under-developed in standard treatments.	Sec. 3
<i>The multipole expansion: point distributions, forces, and torques</i>		
Physical meaning of the dipole moment	Only Landau [16] and Zangwill [6] relate \mathbf{p} to centroids of charge, and only for neutral distributions. No standard reference identifies the resulting point charge distribution explicitly, nor handles the non-neutral case.	Sec. 4
Physical meaning of the quadrupole moment	Panofsky [10] associates it with eccentricity; Zangwill [6] with a moment of inertia. No unified framework relates these descriptions to the underlying charge distribution.	Sec. 4
Construction of point multipoles	Built either by applying differential operators to the Dirac delta or through limiting processes involving arrays of deltas [6, 10, 17]. In both cases, the manipulations operate on an object whose own definition, Eqs. (1)–(2), does not admit derivatives or limits in the classical sense.	Sec. 4
Force on a point dipole	The derivation of the force on a point dipole varies from one text to the next [1, 3, 5, 6, 17]. No standard reference offers a single procedure that also extends to higher-order multipoles.	Sec. 4
Force and torque on multipoles of order ≥ 2	None of the consulted standard references provides a systematic procedure for the force and torque on 2^n -poles of arbitrary order.	Sec. 4
<i>Boundary conditions and boundary value problems</i>		
Derivation of boundary conditions	Obtained by applying the divergence and Stokes theorems to fields that are discontinuous across the interface [1, 3, 5]. As Idemen shows [9], this violates the smoothness hypothesis of the integration theorems, the very hypothesis students have learned in their multivariable calculus courses.	Sec. 5
Physical origin of the boundary conditions	The conditions are presented as the result of geometric manipulations, with the physical identification of each jump term left implicit.	Sec. 5
Setup of boundary value problems	Standard treatments motivate boundary value problems via Green's theorem [5] but import the boundary conditions from the pillbox argument of an earlier chapter, leaving the connection between the physical origin of the conditions and their mathematical role in the BVP implicit.	Sec. 5

2 Distributional tools used in this work

This section collects the notions in the theory of distributions that appear explicitly in Sections 3–5. We restrict ourselves to definitions and operative formulas; the construction of the underlying function spaces, the convergence notions, the convolution and Fourier transforms in the distributional sense, and the proofs of the formulas below are given in a self-contained presentation in Supplementary Material A (provided separately). The presentation in this section follows mainly [9, 18]; rigorous treatments may be found in [13, 19]. We group these tools here for ease of reference. In the classroom we do not present them as a preliminary block but introduce each one at the point where it is needed, as discussed in Section 6.

Distributions as functionals. A *distribution* on \mathbb{R}^3 is a continuous linear functional $T : \mathcal{D}(\mathbb{R}^3) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, where $\mathcal{D}(\mathbb{R}^3)$ denotes the space of test functions (C^∞ functions with compact support). Following Schwartz’s notation, the value of T on the test function φ is written $\langle T, \varphi \rangle$. The space of distributions is denoted $\mathcal{D}'(\mathbb{R}^3)$.

Every locally integrable function f defines a distribution by $\langle f, \varphi \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} f(\mathbf{x})\varphi(\mathbf{x})d^3\mathbf{x}$; such distributions are called *regular*. Distributions that cannot be represented in this way are called *singular*. The fundamental example of a singular distribution is the *Dirac delta* at \mathbf{x}_0 , defined by

$$\langle \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0), \varphi \rangle = \varphi(\mathbf{x}_0). \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) is rigorous and complete. It defines δ as a particular element of \mathcal{D}' without any appeal to the heuristic description as a function *zero at every point except one, where infinite*. Operations performed on δ below, differentiation, multiplication by smooth functions, and limits of sequences, will be *theorems* that follow from this definition rather than identities to be verified case by case against the filtering property.

Derivative of a distribution. The partial derivative of a distribution T is defined by transferring the derivative onto the test function,

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i}, \varphi \right\rangle = - \left\langle T, \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x_i} \right\rangle, \quad i = 1, 2, 3. \quad (4)$$

Under this definition, every distribution is infinitely differentiable. For a regular distribution corresponding to a C^1 function, the distributional derivative coincides with the classical one. When the underlying function has a jump discontinuity, the distributional derivative captures additional singular contributions, as discussed below.

For the particular case $T = \delta$, Eq. (4) yields $\langle \delta', \varphi \rangle = -\varphi'(0)$, which coincides with the integration-by-parts identity stated as *useful* in some standard references [6, Eq. (1.99)]. In those references the identity is checked against the filtering property for each instance. In the framework adopted here it is a particular case of (4) and holds without further verification.

Surface and curve distributions. Let $S \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ be a piecewise smooth surface and $C \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ a piecewise smooth curve. The distributions δ_S and δ_C are defined by

$$\langle \delta_S, \varphi \rangle = \int_S \varphi dS, \quad \langle \delta_C, \varphi \rangle = \int_C \varphi dC. \quad (5)$$

A surface charge density σ on S and a linear density λ on C are represented by the distributions $\sigma\delta_S$ and $\lambda\delta_C$, respectively, with the correct physical dimensions. A point charge q at \mathbf{x}_0 is represented by $q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0)$. All of these are bona fide elements of $\mathcal{D}'(\mathbb{R}^3)$, and a single density symbol ρ can stand for any of them in equations such as Gauss’s law [18].

Distributional differential operators on functions with jump discontinuities. The central technical result of this section is the formula for the gradient, divergence, curl, and Laplacian of a function with a discontinuity across a surface S . Let f be a locally integrable function differentiable away from S , with jump $\llbracket f \rrbracket = f_2 - f_1$ across S in the direction of the unit normal \mathbf{n} pointing from Ω_1 to Ω_2 . Then, in the sense of distributions [9, 18],

$$\nabla f = \{\nabla f\} + \mathbf{n} \llbracket f \rrbracket \delta_S, \quad (6)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{F} = \{\nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}\} + \mathbf{n} \cdot \llbracket \mathbf{F} \rrbracket \delta_S, \quad (7)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{F} = \{\nabla \times \mathbf{F}\} + \mathbf{n} \times \llbracket \mathbf{F} \rrbracket \delta_S, \quad (8)$$

$$\nabla^2 f = \{\nabla^2 f\} + \left[\frac{\partial f}{\partial n} \right] \delta_S + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{n} \llbracket f \rrbracket \delta_S), \quad (9)$$

where $\{\cdot\}$ denotes the differential operator applied within each subdomain (the *regular part*), $\partial f/\partial n = \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla f$ is the normal derivative, and $[[\partial_n f]]$ is its jump. Equations (6)–(9) are the technical core on which the derivation of the boundary conditions in Sec. 5 rests.

The Fourier transform of differential operators. With the convention $\tilde{f}(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int f(\mathbf{x}) e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}} d^3\mathbf{x}$, extended to distributions in the sense of Supplementary Material A (provided separately), the Fourier transform converts the Laplacian into multiplication by $-|\mathbf{k}|^2$:

$$\mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{k}}\{\nabla^2 f\} = -k^2 \tilde{f}(\mathbf{k}), \quad k = |\mathbf{k}|. \quad (10)$$

The convolution theorem, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{k}}\{(f * g)(\mathbf{x})\} = \tilde{f}(\mathbf{k}) \tilde{g}(\mathbf{k})$, also holds in the distributional sense whenever the convolution is well defined. This is the only result from Fourier analysis used in Sec. 3.

3 The electrostatic potential

In their first electromagnetism course, our students build the concept of electrostatic potential in the natural order. They meet Coulomb's force first, then the electric field, and then the potential as the line integral of the field along a path. In the second course it is obtained the other way, axiomatically, starting from Maxwell's equations and arriving at the Poisson equation. The standard references at every level [1–3, 5, 6, 10, 20] follow the same sequence. The potential is first stated for a point charge, then extended by superposition to discrete arrays, and finally generalized to continuous distributions through a separate integral formula for each type of source, volumetric, surface, and line. Each formula is handed over as its own recipe, with no formalism that unifies the cases and no account of why the passage from discrete charges to a continuous density is legitimate. The student is left with one rule per geometry and no principle behind them.

Two further gaps are worth naming, because the present section is built to close them. The first concerns the Green function. Students have usually heard of it, and they associate it vaguely with delta functions, but its meaning is rarely made explicit and most arrive without knowing what it actually represents. The second concerns the Poisson equation. Asked how to solve it, students answer almost reflexively that one uses separation of variables, the method they learned for bounded domains in their mathematical methods course. When asked where the boundary conditions are in the problem at hand, they have no answer, because they have not realized that the Poisson equation is solved in two distinct settings. Over a bounded domain, boundary conditions are essential; over all of space, there are no boundaries.

Sommerfeld [21] draws a distinction that organizes the subject. We bring it to the foreground here, since in our experience students rarely arrive with it. He divides electrostatic phenomena into two categories, *integration problems* and *boundary value problems*. This section addresses the former, where ρ is specified everywhere in space and finding \mathbf{E} reduces to performing an integral; the latter is the subject of Section 5. The distinction is what tells the student why the present section and the boundary value problems are different in kind, rather than two unrelated uses of the same equation. Our aim here is to derive the potential directly from Maxwell's equations using the distributional framework of Section 2, where a single procedure covers every type of charge.

Our analysis begins by considering the electrostatic field equations $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x})$ in vacuum, which in SI units are given by:

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (11)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \epsilon_0^{-1} \rho \quad (12)$$

where ρ is the charge density and ϵ_0 is the electric permittivity of free space in SI units. Equation (11) establishes the non-solenoidal nature of the electrostatic field, while Equation (12) indicates that the electrostatic field's nature is determined by ρ [22]. A point seldom addressed in standard texts is that an elementary unit analysis of Eq. (12) reveals that ρ must be a volumetric charge distribution for the equation to be dimensionally consistent. When this point is made explicit, the student reaction is twofold. Some recognize that they had never questioned the unit balance for non-volumetric charge distributions. Others comment that they had noticed the inconsistency, but since the final result was physically and mathematically sound, they never challenged the procedure. Moreover, in standard texts such as [1, 5, 6], ρ is often used to represent surface, line, or point charges. In our teaching experience, this apparent inconsistency can lead to confusion among students because when dealing with the first exercises of Gauss's Law, the left-hand side of Eq. (12) is integrated over a volume. If ρ represents a non-volumetric distribution of charge (*e.g.*, surface or line charges), then strictly speaking, the right-hand side must be zero because it involves integrating over a set with measure zero in \mathbb{R}^3 [23].

To address this issue, one should consider equation (12) in the context of theory of distributions. That is, both sides of the equality in Gauss's Law must be regarded as linear continuous functionals acting on an arbitrary test function $\varphi(x, y, z)$ in \mathbb{R}^3 . In Schwartz notation this is written as:

$$\forall \varphi \in \mathcal{D} \quad \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}, \varphi \rangle = \epsilon_0^{-1} \langle \rho, \varphi \rangle.$$

As an example of how this approach to Gauss's Law (and more generally to all Maxwell's equations [9]) resolves the units discrepancy, we consider a surface charge density $\rho_S = \sigma \delta_S$ with support on a surface S as explained in Section 2 and measured in coulombs per square meter. In this scenario, we obtain

$$\forall \varphi \in \mathcal{D} \quad \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}, \varphi \rangle = \epsilon_0^{-1} \langle \rho_S, \varphi \rangle,$$

explicitly

$$\forall \varphi \in \mathcal{D} \quad \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} d^3\mathbf{x} = \epsilon_0^{-1} \int_S \sigma \varphi dS.$$

In this fashion we can see that there is no problem regarding the units of the charge density because this equality has the same units.

Once the nature of the charge distributions has been elucidated, we can proceed to solve Maxwell's equations for the electrostatic field, specifically equations (11) and (12). The former equation implies that the electric field can be expressed as $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}) = -\nabla\phi(\mathbf{x})$. After substituting Eq. (12), we obtain the Poisson equation

$$\nabla^2\phi = -\epsilon_0^{-1}\rho. \quad (13)$$

By this point in our course the students have already seen the *Helmholtz theorem* [1, 6], which establishes that a vector field can be reconstructed from its curl and its divergence. We use it here to introduce the idea that the Poisson equation combines the information of both, so that solving it allows to retrieve the electric field. In cases where necessary, this equation should be interpreted in the sense of distributions. The solution can be obtained by means of the Fourier transform ($\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{k}$) using Eq. (10). Therefore Eq. (13) can be written as:

$$-(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{k})\tilde{\phi}(\mathbf{k}) = -\epsilon_0^{-1}\tilde{\rho}(\mathbf{k}).$$

This equation can also be expressed more clearly as

$$\tilde{\phi}(\mathbf{k}) = \tilde{G}(\mathbf{k})\tilde{\rho}(\mathbf{k}), \quad (14)$$

where

$$\tilde{G}(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0 k^2}, \quad k = |\mathbf{k}|$$

is the Fourier transform of the so-called Green's function in electrostatics. Let us notice that equation (14) neatly separates the information needed to obtain the electrostatic potential. First, one must know where and how the charges are distributed, which is given by the density $\tilde{\rho}$, and which varies from one problem to another. Second, \tilde{G} carries the information about the differential operator in Eq. (13), that is, about how the charge distribution determines the electrostatic potential.

In order to explore the role played by the Green's function G we will consider the differential equation it satisfies, that is:

$$\nabla^2 G(\mathbf{x}) = -\epsilon_0^{-1}(2\pi)^3 \delta(\mathbf{x}), \quad (15)$$

as follows from the distributional Fourier identity (Supplementary Material A). The $(2\pi)^3$ factor is a direct consequence of our Fourier transform convention and has no physical relevance.

Equation (15) mirrors the role of the electrostatic potential in Eq. (13), where the source is proportional to a point charge distribution localized at the origin of coordinates. This can be seen more clearly by taking its inverse Fourier transform ($\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{x}$) given by

$$G(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \tilde{G}(\mathbf{k}) e^{-i\mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{k}} d^3\mathbf{k}.$$

This integral can be calculated after performing the change of variables $k_x = k \sin \theta \cos \phi$, $k_y = k \sin \theta \sin \phi$ and $k_z = k \cos \theta$, where $k = |\mathbf{k}|$ and θ is the angle between \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{k} , and considering a contour integration in the complex plane [24]. Thus the Green function is explicitly given by

$$G(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{(2\pi)^3}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x}|}. \quad (16)$$

Let us remark on what G is, since the point is a common source of confusion. It is tempting to call G the potential of a point charge, but that reading is not quite right. A point charge carries units of coulombs, whereas G carries none. What G represents is the response of the differential operator to a fundamental point source, the potential the system produces for an excitation localized at the origin, before any charge is assigned. The charge enters later, through the density in the convolution. The electrostatic potential ϕ is recovered by inverting Eq. (14), which by the convolution theorem (Supplementary Material A) reads

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = (G * \rho)(\mathbf{x}),$$

where $*$ denotes the convolution and $G(\mathbf{x})$ is given by Eq. (16). Read this way, the convolution is nothing more than placing that fundamental response at every point of space, weighted by how much charge sits there and of what sign. Superposition is then not a principle to be assumed but a consequence one can see in the formula. For a volumetric charge distribution ρ the electrostatic potential reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(\mathbf{x}) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3} G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \rho(\mathbf{y}) d^3 \mathbf{y}, \\ &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \frac{(2\pi)^3}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \rho(\mathbf{y}) d^3 \mathbf{y}, \\ &= \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \frac{\rho(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} d^3 \mathbf{y}. \end{aligned}$$

From this last expression, it is clear that the electrostatic potential can be interpreted as the total contribution of the potentials generated by point charges localized at every \mathbf{y} , each modulated by the volumetric density of charge ρ , which gives the magnitude and sign of the point charge at that location.

For non-volumetric charge densities, the convolution must be taken in the distributional sense (Supplementary Material A). To illustrate the procedure, consider the one-dimensional charge distribution $\rho_\lambda(\mathbf{x}) = \lambda(\mathbf{x})\delta_C$ where C is a curve in space and λ is a charge linear density defined on C . As we know, the units of λ are coulomb per meter. The electrostatic potential $\phi_\lambda(\mathbf{x})$ is given by:

$$\phi_\lambda(\mathbf{x}) = (G * \lambda\delta_C)(\mathbf{x}).$$

Unfolding the distributional convolution and using the action of $\lambda\delta_C$ on a test function (the detailed calculation is given in Supplementary Material A, §S2.1), one obtains

$$\phi_\lambda(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in C} \frac{\lambda(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} dC,$$

which is found in many textbooks as [1, 7]. It could be argued that this is a cumbersome procedure to derive a well-known result in electrostatics. However, it should be emphasized that this is a formal deduction derived directly from Maxwell's equations, without relying on the superposition principle or on the somewhat heuristic approach of *taking the distributions to the continuum*. Furthermore, for any $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ one can interpret the potential ϕ_λ as the distribution $\lambda(\mathbf{y})\delta_C$ applied to the function $\frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|}$, that is:

$$\phi_\lambda(\mathbf{x}) = \left\langle \lambda(\mathbf{y})\delta_C, \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right\rangle.$$

This process can be similarly applied to other kinds of charge densities. Although $\frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|}$ is not a test function, it enters into the categories for which distributions can still be applied, since it is integrable on any sphere centered on \mathbf{y} and decays to zero as $|\mathbf{x}| \rightarrow \infty$, as explained in [18]. Generalizing this result we can write

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \left\langle \rho(\mathbf{y}), \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right\rangle \quad (17)$$

where $\rho(\mathbf{y})$ can be either a volume, surface, line, or point charge density. The electrostatic field $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x})$ follows by taking the negative gradient. Equation (17) is the starting point for the multipole expansion of the next section.

4 The multipole expansion: Point distributions, forces, and torques

Once the electrostatic potential is available as the integral of Section 3, computing it for a given charge distribution is, in principle, a solved problem. In practice it is not. Before reaching this topic we set our students problems on distributions such as a charge along an Archimedean spiral or opposite charges on the two sheets of a hyperboloid, asking them to set up the potential but leaving the integral indicated. They correctly observe that these integrals have no closed form and could only be evaluated numerically. A numerical value, however, permits little analysis. Now imagine the charge distribution of an everyday object, a cat or a chair. Its potential can in principle be written as an integral, but that integral tells us almost nothing we can reason about. What is needed is a different way of attacking the problem, a universal language in which the potential of any charge distribution can be analyzed rather than merely computed. That language is the multipole expansion. Our students have already met it in their first electromagnetism course, but usually as the statement that, far away, the potential is that of a single charge, to which the contributions of a dipole and then a quadrupole are added as one looks closer, without any account of where this sequence of contributions comes from.

In standard references, the multipole expansion is derived through a Cartesian Taylor series [1, 3, 10] or the spherical addition theorem [5, 6, 8], and students learn to attach the standard names to each term, but beyond identifying the zeroth moment with the total charge, the physical meaning of the higher moments is rarely made explicit. This is not only a difficulty for students; the references themselves are not fully consistent about it. Panofsky [10] associates the quadrupole with the eccentricity of the distribution and Zangwill [6] with a moment of inertia, while only Landau [16] and Zangwill [6] connect the dipole moment to centroids of charge, and only for neutral distributions. No standard reference gives a unified physical interpretation of the three principal moments. Nor is the relation between the expansion of an extended distribution and the point multipoles from which the terms take their names ever made explicit. There is also a silent shift from the extended distribution to point objects. The charge distributions that produce the dipole and quadrupole potentials are introduced, with no transition, by applying differential operators to the Dirac delta, or by limiting processes on arrays of deltas [6, 10, 17], manipulations performed on an object whose own definition, the integral property of Eq. (1) or the informal prescription of Eq. (2), admits neither derivatives nor limits in the classical sense. The student is thus asked to differentiate something that cannot be differentiated, in order to name an object that cannot be located. Finally, the derivations of the force on a point dipole vary from one text to the next [1, 3, 5, 6, 17], and none provides a systematic procedure for the force and torque on higher-order multipoles (2^n -poles).

The difficulty in teaching this material is that three things must be understood together, and the standard presentation separates them. The first is the purpose. The Taylor expansion is applied to extended charge distributions, which are what the physics is about. The second is the vocabulary. An extended distribution is intractable on its own, so one needs a language of simpler point objects in which to analyze it. The third is the act of truncating, which is precisely what produces that language. The student usually reads the truncation as discarding detail for convenience, when it is in fact a reorganization of the potential in terms of contributions of point multipoles, objects that can be understood one at a time. The purpose, the vocabulary, and the act of truncating are a single idea, and presenting them separately is what leaves the student with a slogan instead of a method. To use the expansion as a language rather than a slogan, we build it from the Taylor series, first for point objects and then for extended distributions. The construction of the point multipoles that occupies the next two subsections is deliberately formal. For the moment we set the integrals aside and work only with the Taylor series and point objects, developing the vocabulary before returning, in Section 4.3, to the extended distributions where the physics resides. In what follows the point multipoles acquire an explicit charge representation, the moments acquire a physical interpretation, and the force and torque follow in closed form for arbitrary order.

4.1 The Point Multipoles

The multipole expansion rests on the Taylor expansion of $1/|\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{x}'|$ for $|\mathbf{x}| > |\boldsymbol{x}'|$. We consider the Lagrange form and its remainder rather than an infinite series, because it is what gives a face to the information the truncation discards and lets the student see what the polynomial part preserves. Recall the Taylor expansion of a function $F : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with this remainder. Using the auxiliary function $\mathbf{g}(\eta) = \mathbf{x} - \eta\boldsymbol{x}'$, so that $F(\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{x}')$ corresponds to the value at $\eta = 1$ of the

composition $F \circ \mathbf{g}$, and applying the chain rule $d^n/d\eta^n F = [-\mathbf{x}' \cdot \nabla]^n F$, one obtains

$$F(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}') = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{[-\mathbf{x}' \cdot \nabla]^n}{n!} F(\mathbf{x}) + \frac{[-\mathbf{x}' \cdot \nabla]^{N+1}}{(N+1)!} F(\mathbf{x} - \xi \mathbf{x}'), \quad \xi \in [0, 1].$$

Since the Dirac delta distribution $\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_1)$ is not a function, this expansion cannot be applied to it directly. It can instead be obtained from the effect of the delta on a test function $\varphi(\mathbf{x})$, following Raimond [25] and Scharf [26] (see also Section 2).

$$\langle \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_1), \varphi(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \langle \delta(\mathbf{x}), \varphi(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x}_1) \rangle = \varphi(\mathbf{x}_1).$$

Expanding $\varphi(\mathbf{x}_1)$ in a Taylor series around the origin yields:

$$\varphi(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{[\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^n}{n!} \varphi(\mathbf{x}) + \frac{[\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^{N+1}}{(N+1)!} \varphi(\xi \mathbf{x}_1), \quad \xi \in [0, 1]. \quad (18)$$

To obtain the Taylor expansion in the sense of distributions, one expresses Equation (18) as the action of an unknown distribution on $\varphi(\mathbf{x})$ and determines this distribution by analyzing each term of the series. A straightforward induction (provided in Supplementary Material A, §S2.2) yields the identity

$$\frac{[\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^n \varphi(\mathbf{0})}{n!} = \left\langle \frac{[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^n \delta(\mathbf{x})}{n!}, \varphi(\mathbf{x}) \right\rangle,$$

together with the analogous expression for the Lagrange remainder. Thus, the Taylor expansion of $\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_1)$ reads

$$\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^n \delta(\mathbf{x})}{n!} + \frac{[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^{N+1} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \xi \mathbf{x}_1)}{(N+1)!}.$$

Next, we will apply the formalism derived earlier to obtain what is commonly referred to as point multipoles. As established in the literature (*e.g.* [5, 8]), the charge density representing a point charge with magnitude q localized at position $\mathbf{x}_0 + s\mathbf{x}_1$, where s is a dimensionless parameter, is given by $q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0 - s\mathbf{x}_1)$. Therefore, considering the Taylor expansion, in the sense of distributions, around \mathbf{x}_0 with $N = 1$ one has:

$$q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0 - s\mathbf{x}_1) = q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) + [-s\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) + \frac{1}{2}[-s\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^2 q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0 - s\xi \mathbf{x}_1), \quad \xi \in [0, 1].$$

By dividing over s and after some elementary manipulations, this expression can be rearranged as follows:

$$[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) = \frac{q}{s}\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0 - s\mathbf{x}_1) - \frac{q}{s}\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) - s\frac{1}{2}[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^2 q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0 - s\xi \mathbf{x}_1), \quad \xi \in [0, 1].$$

The left-hand side of this expression describes the application of the operator $[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]$ to the charge distribution $q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0)$, which represents a point charge located at \mathbf{x}_0 . On the right-hand side we have a physical dipole, where the positive point charge with magnitude $\frac{q}{s}$ is located at $\mathbf{x}_0 + s\mathbf{x}_1$ and the corresponding negative charge is located at \mathbf{x}_0 , together with a Lagrange remainder scaled by a factor of s . We find it useful to present the operator $[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]$ to the students as a *dipole creator*, since applied to a monopole it produces a pair of opposite charges plus the scaled remainder. We then ask how the approximation error might be removed, and students usually arrive on their own at the limit, taken in the sense of Supplementary Material A, as $s \rightarrow 0$:

$$[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{q}{s}\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0 - s\mathbf{x}_1) - \frac{q}{s}\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) \right].$$

Returning to the physics of this last expression, the charge distribution $[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0)$ corresponds to a pair of point charges of opposite sign that get closer and closer while their magnitudes grow without bound, in such a way as not to lose the dipole character. This is what is known as a point, or pure, dipole [6, 8], and the vector $\mathbf{p} = q\mathbf{x}_1$ is called the dipole moment. The distinction between this point dipole and the physical dipole of finite separation s is mentioned in standard textbooks [1, 4], but it is rarely presented as what it is, the limit of a distribution. Here it arises explicitly as the $s \rightarrow 0$ limit of the construction, and the physical meaning of the moment \mathbf{p} will be given later.

Applying the dipole creator once more, now to the point dipole rather than to the monopole, produces a dipole of a dipole, which is the quadrupole. The students already anticipate the construction by analogy, applying $[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]$ twice to $q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0)$ and taking $s \rightarrow 0$:

$$[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^2 q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{q}{s^2} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0 - 2s\mathbf{x}_1) - 2\frac{q}{s^2} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0 - s\mathbf{x}_1) + \frac{q}{s^2} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) \right]. \quad (19)$$

This charge distribution was previously obtained by Panofsky [10], though using the electrostatic potential in spherical coordinates rather than the charge distribution directly. Two observations are worth highlighting in the classroom. First, the arrangement in Eq. (19) consists of three charges placed on the line connecting \mathbf{x}_0 and $\mathbf{x}_0 + 2s\mathbf{x}_1$, a *linear* configuration, not the four-charge parallelogram often presented to students as the canonical point quadrupole. This result usually surprises the students, who had always accepted the textbook representation without questioning it. Second, the charge magnitudes scale as q/s^2 rather than q/s . We ask the students to picture this as replicating the quadrupole field with three Van de Graaff generators. If the devices are brought together linearly, in steps of s , their charges must grow quadratically, as q/s^2 , for the quadrupolar structure to survive the limit. This kind of observation, we tell them, is exactly what must be weighed once an actual experimental arrangement is built, since it sets the limit up to which the ideal mathematical object can approximate reality.

Each further application of the dipole creator pairs the previous configuration with a shifted copy of itself, so that by induction one obtains, for the 2^n -pole point distribution,

$$[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^n q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \left[\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{n-k} \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!} \frac{q}{s^n} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0 - ks\mathbf{x}_1) \right]. \quad (20)$$

To the best of our knowledge, this explicit representation has never been reported.

This construction also explains the names. The dipole is a pair built from the monopole, the quadrupole is a pair of dipoles, and the 2^n -pole is reached by n successive pairings. The factor 2^n in the name is therefore not a convention but a count of the charges in the limiting configuration, a fact the operator representation makes immediate and that the spherical-harmonic presentation leaves opaque.

Once the point multipoles are well understood, we derive the electrostatic potential of a point monopole $\rho_1(\mathbf{y}) = q\delta(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}_0)$, which follows from Eq. (17) by applying the charge distribution to the function $\frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|}$ in Schwartz's notation:

$$\phi_1(\mathbf{x}) = \left\langle q\delta(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}_0), \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right\rangle = \frac{q}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0|}. \quad (21)$$

For the students, this is another instance at which the formalism developed earlier shows its reach, since the same operation, the action of the charge distribution on the function $\frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|}$, produces the potential of any charge distribution they apply it to. For the point dipole $\rho_2(\mathbf{y}) = [-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{y}}]q\delta(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}_0)$, the same procedure shows how the differential operator transfers from the distribution to the function $\frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|}$. Using the definition of the distributional derivative and the identity $\nabla_{\mathbf{y}}(1/|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|) = -\nabla_{\mathbf{x}}(1/|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|)$, one obtains

$$\phi_2(\mathbf{x}) = [-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{x}}] \frac{q}{4\pi\epsilon_0 |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0|} = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{\mathbf{p} \cdot (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0)}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0|^3},$$

where $\mathbf{p} = q\mathbf{x}_1$ is the dipole moment vector. The dipole potential is thus the result of applying $[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{x}}]$ to the monopole potential of Eq. (21).

In general, the electrostatic potential generated by the 2^n -pole point distribution $\rho_{2^n}(\mathbf{y}) = [-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{y}}]^n q\delta(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}_0)$, namely $\phi_{2^n}(\mathbf{x})$, can be retrieved by means of Eq. (17), that is

$$\phi_{2^n}(\mathbf{x}) = [-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{x}}]^n \frac{q}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0|}. \quad (22)$$

With this, the students reach what the standard presentation leaves implicit. The mathematical expression of each point multipole is now tied to the charge distribution that produces it, the two read off from a single operator, closing the gap between the named terms of the expansion and the objects behind them. The electrostatic field produced by a point multipole then follows by taking the negative gradient of its potential.

4.2 Force and torque exerted on a point multipole

Students can write the force on a point charge but are rarely shown how to obtain the force or torque between higher multipoles, and they do not see why it would be needed. The reason is practical. The force between two extended distributions is, in general, a multiple integral that cannot be carried out in closed form, whereas once each distribution is replaced by its point-multipole equivalents the interaction reduces to evaluating the closed-form expressions derived here. As will become apparent in Section 4.3, this reduction generally requires terms beyond the dipole, so the force and torque on a point distribution must be available for arbitrary order n , not only for $n = 1$.

In elementary textbooks (e.g. [1, 3, 22]), the force exerted by an external field \mathbf{E}_{ext} on a point charge of magnitude q is written

$$\mathbf{F} = q\mathbf{E}_{\text{ext}},$$

without emphasizing that \mathbf{E}_{ext} must be evaluated at the location of the charge. For a volumetric distribution ρ , the Lorentz force takes the integral form [5, 7]

$$\mathbf{F} = \int_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \rho(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{E}_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{x}) d^3\mathbf{x},$$

which assumes ρ to be a function and therefore does not accommodate the point multipoles of Eq. (20). The distributional generalization is to apply ρ to each component of \mathbf{E}_{ext} :

$$F_i = \langle \rho(\mathbf{x}), E_{\text{ext},i}(\mathbf{x}) \rangle, \quad i = 1, 2, 3.$$

For example, the force exerted by an external electrostatic field \mathbf{E}_{ext} on a point charge $\rho_0(\mathbf{x}) = q_0\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0)$ is

$$F_{0,i} = \langle q_0\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0), E_{\text{ext},i}(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = q_0 E_{\text{ext},i}(\mathbf{x}_0), \quad i = 1, 2, 3.$$

This yields the well-known expression for the Lorentz force on a point charge:

$$\mathbf{F}_0 = q_0 \mathbf{E}_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{x}_0). \quad (23)$$

If \mathbf{E}_{ext} corresponds to the field generated by a point charge $q_1\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_1)$, Eq. (23) recovers Coulomb's force:

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{q_0 q_1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{(\mathbf{x}_0 - \mathbf{x}_1)}{|\mathbf{x}_0 - \mathbf{x}_1|^3}.$$

For the dipole $\rho_2 = [-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]q_0\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0)$, applying the distribution to $E_{\text{ext},i}$ transfers the derivative onto the field:

$$F_{1,i} = \langle [-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]q_0\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0), E_{\text{ext},i}(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla q_0 E_{\text{ext},i}(\mathbf{x}_0). \quad (24)$$

Recognizing $q_0 E_{\text{ext},i}(\mathbf{x}_0)$ as the components of the monopole force, applying the vector identity $\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla \mathbf{F}_0 = \mathbf{x}_1 \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{F}_0) + \nabla(\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \mathbf{F}_0)$, and using $\nabla \times \mathbf{F}_0 = \mathbf{0}$ (since $\mathbf{F}_0 \propto \mathbf{E}_{\text{ext}}$ is irrotational), one obtains

$$\mathbf{F}_1 = \nabla(\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \mathbf{F}_0(\mathbf{x}_0)). \quad (25)$$

This expression is the same as the one obtained in the literature (e.g. [1, 3, 6]), albeit in a more straightforward manner. Using induction, it can be proved that the Lorentz force \mathbf{F}_n exerted on a 2^n -pole given by Eq. (20) by an external electrostatic field is

$$\mathbf{F}_n = \underbrace{\nabla(\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \dots \nabla(\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \mathbf{F}_0(\mathbf{x}_0)) \dots)}_{n \text{ times}}. \quad (26)$$

The procedure for obtaining the torque exerted by an external electrostatic field \mathbf{E}_{ext} on a point multipole is similar to the one used for the Lorentz force. The torque on a volumetric charge density ρ is

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \int_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \mathbf{x} \times \rho(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{E}_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{x}) d^3\mathbf{x},$$

and its natural extension in the theory of distributions is

$$\tau_i = \epsilon_{ijk} \langle \rho, x_j E_{\text{ext},k} \rangle,$$

where ϵ_{ijk} denotes the Levi-Civita symbol [27]. For the torque exerted on a monopole $\boldsymbol{\tau}_0$ one has

$$\tau_{0,i} = \epsilon_{ijk} \langle q\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0), x_j E_{ext,k}(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \epsilon_{ijk} x_{0,j} q E_{ext,k}(\mathbf{x}_0),$$

so that the torque is

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_0 = \mathbf{x}_0 \times \mathbf{F}_0(\mathbf{x}_0).$$

For the torque $\boldsymbol{\tau}_1$ on a point dipole, an analogous calculation, transferring the derivative onto $x_j E_{ext,k}$ through the action of the distribution and applying the Leibniz rule, yields

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_1 = \mathbf{x}_1 \times \mathbf{F}_0 + \mathbf{x}_0 \times \mathbf{F}_1. \quad (27)$$

Recalling that $\mathbf{p} = q\mathbf{x}_1$ is the dipole moment, the first term reads $\mathbf{p} \times \mathbf{E}_{ext}(\mathbf{x}_0)$, the well-known torque that tends to align the dipole with the external field [1]; the second term $\mathbf{x}_0 \times \mathbf{F}_1$ is the torque due to the net force on the dipole. The complete expression agrees with that reported by Zangwill [6]. Applying the same procedure to the 2^n -multipole yields the general expression

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_n = n\mathbf{x}_1 \times \mathbf{F}_{n-1} + \mathbf{x}_0 \times \mathbf{F}_n, \quad (28)$$

where the force \mathbf{F}_n is given by Eq. (26). This result, together with the general force of Eq. (26), was not found in our literature review, and shows the power of the theory of distributions to reach such expressions without ad hoc manipulations.

These formulas acquire a concrete meaning through a thought experiment we pose in class. Suppose we are given a point monopole, a point dipole, and a point quadrupole, and asked to tell them apart. Mapping the full electric field of each would distinguish them, but that would require filling space with probes, plastic beads or seeds suspended in oil. A more economical test is to place each one in the uniform field of a parallel-plate capacitor. The monopole is the only one that experiences a net force there and so the only one that translates, since the force on the dipole and on the quadrupole vanishes in a constant field. The dipole and the quadrupole are then told apart by the torque, which is nonzero for the dipole and zero for the quadrupole. Each object is thus identified by the lowest order at which its force or torque fails to vanish, and the expressions derived above for arbitrary order are what make such reasoning systematic rather than case by case. The answer can be reasoned out on physical grounds, drawing on the intuition the students built in their first electromagnetism course, but without the closed-form force and torque derived above it would remain a plausible guess. Here the intuition and the formalism meet, the first reaching the answer and the second establishing it for a multipole of any order.

4.3 Extended charge distributions via reduction to point multipoles

Up to this point, the multipole expansion has been developed as a sequence of formal constructions. The point multipoles are objects of interest in their own right, and the forces and torques on them are given by Eqs. (26) and (28) for arbitrary order n . Yet the physical problems an instructor faces are problems about extended charge distributions, not about point multipoles. Students perform the Taylor expansion on an electrostatic potential created by a volumetric ρ but do not connect the multipole terms of the extended charge with their point counterparts, which is exactly what the expansion is for.

The multipole expansion provides the bridge between the two descriptions. In what follows we show that the standard Taylor expansion of $1/|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$, applied to an extended distribution, yields a series whose terms are related to the potentials of the point multipoles constructed in Section 4.1. The reduction to point objects is not, however, equally clean at every order, and this is one of the points we most want the students to see. The monopole and dipole terms reduce exactly to a point monopole and a point dipole. From the quadrupole onward this is no longer the case. The quadrupole term splits into a point quadrupole plus a volumetric contribution that cannot be absorbed into any point object, an irreducible remnant of the extended distribution. The structure suggests that such volumetric corrections persist, and grow more involved, at higher orders, though we do not prove this here. We therefore develop the reduction for the monopole, dipole, and quadrupole, which is as far as an electrostatics course ordinarily goes. The behavior beyond the quadrupole is a question in its own right and a direction for further work.

A problem on the extended distribution can then be addressed by computing the moments to the desired order, replacing the distribution by its point-multipole equivalents together with the extended correction where it appears, and applying the force and torque formulas of Section 4.2. The expansion need not terminate at the dipole, since a quadrupolar or higher-order correction may be required for the desired accuracy. We now construct the reduction term by term for a volumetric ρ , the results applying equally to surface and line distributions.

The expansion. Following the standard procedure, the Taylor expansion of $1/|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$ for $|\mathbf{x}| > |\mathbf{y}|$ yields

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{n!} \phi_n(\mathbf{x}) + R_{N+1}(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{y}), \quad (29)$$

where the remainder R_{N+1} quantifies the truncation error and

$$\phi_n(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3} [-\mathbf{y} \cdot \nabla]^n \frac{\rho(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x}|} d^3\mathbf{y}.$$

Applied to the extended density ρ , the operator $[-\mathbf{y} \cdot \nabla]^n$ produces a multipole charge density of order n , and ϕ_n is the potential of that density. This is the same operator that, in Section 4.1, turned a point charge $q\delta$ into a point multipole, acting now on ρ rather than on a delta. The identification of ρ with its point-multipole equivalent at each order is what we now make explicit, term by term, through the physical interpretation of the moments.

Monopole ($n = 0$): total charge. The monopole term is

$$\phi_0(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Q_0}{|\mathbf{x}|}, \quad Q_0 = \int_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \rho(\mathbf{y}) d^3\mathbf{y}.$$

This is the potential generated by a point charge Q_0 at the origin. The point-multipole equivalent of ρ at this order is the monopole $Q_0\delta(\mathbf{y})$. Standard textbooks arrive at the same expression, but without identifying the underlying charge distribution explicitly, since the delta language is typically not employed. As a thought experiment we return to the cat that opened the section. As an everyday neutral object it has $Q_0 = 0$, so its monopole term vanishes. We then imagine rubbing it with a comb, and now $Q_0 \neq 0$. The point students take away is that the monopole moment is nothing more abstract than the net charge, and that it is the first and coarsest feature the expansion records about any distribution.

Dipole ($n = 1$): centers of charge. The dipole term is

$$\phi_1(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{\mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{p}}{|\mathbf{x}|^3}, \quad \mathbf{p} = \int_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \mathbf{y} \rho(\mathbf{y}) d^3\mathbf{y}, \quad (30)$$

the potential of a point dipole of moment \mathbf{p} at the origin. To identify the point-dipole equivalent of ρ operationally, we need to relate \mathbf{p} to physical features of the distribution. In standard references [1, 5, 10] no explicit physical interpretation of \mathbf{p} is given; we provide one by generalizing Landau's treatment for a neutral array of point charges [16].

Starting by defining

$$\rho^\pm(\mathbf{y}) = \frac{|\rho(\mathbf{y})| \pm \rho(\mathbf{y})}{2}, \quad (31)$$

which satisfy $\rho^\pm \geq 0$ and $\rho = \rho^+ - \rho^-$. The corresponding total charges Q^\pm and centers of charge \mathbf{y}^\pm are

$$Q^\pm = \int \rho^\pm d^3\mathbf{y}, \quad \mathbf{y}^\pm = \frac{1}{Q^\pm} \int \mathbf{y} \rho^\pm d^3\mathbf{y}.$$

Assuming $Q^+, Q^- \neq 0$ (the case where one vanishes is trivial), Eq. (30) gives $\mathbf{p} = Q^+\mathbf{y}^+ - Q^-\mathbf{y}^-$. Setting

$$Q_{dip} = \max(Q^+, Q^-), \quad Q'_{dip} = \min(Q^+, Q^-), \quad \alpha = \frac{Q'_{dip}}{Q_{dip}} \in (0, 1],$$

with \mathbf{y}_{dip} and \mathbf{y}'_{dip} the corresponding centers of charge, one obtains

$$\mathbf{p} = Q_{dip}(\mathbf{y}_{dip} - \alpha \mathbf{y}'_{dip}). \quad (32)$$

The parameter α quantifies the charge imbalance between ρ^+ and ρ^- . When $\alpha = 1$ the distribution is neutral and \mathbf{p} points from the center of the negative charges to the center of the positive charges, recovering the classical interpretation [16]; in the general case, \mathbf{p} measures the weighted displacement between the two centers of charge, modulated by α .

Substituting Eq. (32) into Eq. (30), ϕ_1 coincides with the potential generated by the point dipole distribution

$$\rho_1(\mathbf{y}) = [-(\mathbf{y}_{dip} - \alpha \mathbf{y}'_{dip}) \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{y}}] Q_{dip} \delta(\mathbf{y}),$$

localized at the origin. This is the point-multipole equivalent of ρ at first order: given the distribution, compute \mathbf{y}_{dip} , \mathbf{y}'_{dip} , Q_{dip} , α , and the extended dipolar interaction reduces to one with the point dipole above, on which the formulas of Section 4.2 apply directly.

This general analysis is not given explicitly in any text we consulted, with the partial exception of Landau, already credited above for the neutral case. Two things make the result worth dwelling on in class. The first is what it does for the cat. An unrubbed cat, being neutral, has no monopole term, and through the lens of the expansion its leading contribution is dipolar, so we read it as a dipole. Once rubbed, it acquires a monopole term as well, and we read it as a monopole with a dipolar correction. The same object yields different multipole expansions depending on its state, which is exactly the habit of thinking in terms of charges that we want the students to acquire. The second is the meaning it gives to the dipole moment vector. In their first electromagnetism course \mathbf{p} is typically defined and then used, with no account of what it represents. Here it acquires a concrete meaning, the weighted displacement between the centers of positive and negative charge of a distribution, extended or not, which students find satisfying in a way the bare definition never was.

Quadrupole ($n = 2$): moments of inertia. The quadrupole term reads, after factoring $\hat{\mathbf{n}} = \mathbf{x}/|\mathbf{x}|$,

$$\phi_2(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x}|^3} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \rho(\mathbf{y}) (3(\mathbf{y} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}})^2 - |\mathbf{y}|^2) d^3\mathbf{y}.$$

Standard treatments (e.g. [5, 6]) cast this as the quadratic form $\hat{\mathbf{n}}^T \overleftrightarrow{Q} \hat{\mathbf{n}}/|\mathbf{x}|^2$ and discuss the tensor \overleftrightarrow{Q} geometrically, but without identifying the underlying point-multipole equivalent.

Proceeding as for the dipole, write $\phi_2(\mathbf{x}) = \phi_2^+(\mathbf{x}) - \phi_2^-(\mathbf{x})$ with ρ^\pm defined in Eq. (31). Translating each ϕ_2^\pm by the centroid \mathbf{x}^\pm of ρ^\pm , the integrand decomposes naturally (Supplementary Material A, S2.2) into

$$\phi_2^\pm(\mathbf{x}) = \phi_{2,\text{point}}^\pm(\mathbf{x}) + \phi_{2,\text{extended}}^\pm(\mathbf{x}), \quad (33)$$

where

$$\phi_{2,\text{point}}^\pm(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Q^\pm}{|\mathbf{x}|^3} (3(\mathbf{x}^\pm \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}})^2 - |\mathbf{x}^\pm|^2)$$

is the potential of a point quadrupole at the origin generated by the distribution $\rho_{2,\text{point}}^\pm = [-\mathbf{x}^\pm \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{y}}]^2 Q^\pm \delta(\mathbf{y})$, and the extended contribution can be cast in spherical coordinates centered at \mathbf{x}^\pm as

$$\phi_{2,\text{extended}}^\pm(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Q^\pm C^\pm}{|\mathbf{x}|^3}, \quad C^\pm = 2 \int \frac{\rho^\pm(\mathbf{y})}{Q^\pm} P_2(\cos \vartheta) d^3\mathbf{y},$$

with P_2 the Legendre polynomial of degree two and ϑ the angle between $\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm$ and $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$. The shape factor C^\pm measures how much the normalized distribution ρ^\pm/Q^\pm , centered at \mathbf{x}^\pm , resembles the angular pattern $r^2 P_2(\cos \vartheta)$ as seen from the observer direction.

A vector decomposition of the integrand (Supplementary Material A, §S2.4) recasts both contributions as moments of inertia. Combining the two:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_2^\pm(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Q^\pm}{|\mathbf{x}|^3} & \left[\underbrace{2 \left(|\hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{x}^\pm \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}})|^2 + \int \frac{\rho^\pm}{Q^\pm} |(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}|^2 d^3\mathbf{y} \right)}_{\text{parallel moment of inertia (about } \hat{\mathbf{n}})} \right. \\ & \left. - \underbrace{\left(|\mathbf{x}^\pm - \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{x}^\pm \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}})|^2 + \int \frac{\rho^\pm}{Q^\pm} |(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) - \hat{\mathbf{n}}((\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}})|^2 d^3\mathbf{y} \right)}_{\text{perpendicular moment of inertia (about the plane } \perp \hat{\mathbf{n}})} \right]. \quad (34) \end{aligned}$$

The sign and magnitude of ϕ_2^\pm are therefore determined by the competition between the moments of inertia of ρ^\pm parallel and perpendicular to the observer. A prolate configuration, with charge concentrated along $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$, produces a positive quadrupole potential, and an oblate configuration produces a negative one.

Two points deserve emphasis here. The first is the limit of the point reduction announced at the start of this section. The point quadrupole $\phi_{2,\text{point}}^\pm$ is the part that reduces to a point object, but the term $\phi_{2,\text{extended}}^\pm$, carried by the shape factor C^\pm , does not. It is the volumetric remnant of the distribution, and it cannot be absorbed into any point multipole. This is the order at which the reduction to point objects ceases to be exact, and the formalism shows exactly where and why. The

second is what the result does for the cat. Having seen it as a monopole through its net charge and as a dipole through its centers of charge, the students now see it as a quadrupole through its moments of inertia, the same object read at a finer resolution.

Taken together, the three terms show what the multipole expansion is for. The integral expression of the potential holds all the information about the charge distribution at once, bound together and inaccessible to analysis. The expansion separates that information into pieces that can be read one at a time. The monopole tells how much charge there is, the dipole the imbalance between the centers of positive and negative charge, and the quadrupole the moments of inertia of the distribution. What was locked inside a single integral is now laid out term by term, available for the analysis we set out to perform at the start of the section. The behavior beyond the quadrupole, where the volumetric corrections grow more involved, is a natural direction for further work.

5 Boundary value problems in electrostatics

In Section 3 we addressed the integration problems described by Sommerfeld [21]. We now turn to the second type of problem: boundary value problems, in which ρ is not fully specified throughout space but is partially determined by the materials present in different spatial domains. We examine two interfaces relevant to undergraduate study: between two simple dielectrics, and between a simple dielectric and an ideal ohmic conductor.

The passage of the electrostatic field across material interfaces is governed by the boundary conditions on its tangential and normal components. Students reach this point already confident in the standard derivation, for three reasons that reinforce one another. It appears in every textbook [1, 3, 5], the geometric picture of a pillbox straddling the interface and a rectangular loop across it feels natural, and the argument delivers the correct conditions. That last point is the one that hides the difficulty. A student who arrives at the right result infers that the method must be sound, but a method can reach a correct result for the wrong reasons, and this is such a case.

We make the point in class rather than assert it. Students reproduce the pillbox and rectangular-loop derivation without hesitation, and when asked whether anything is wrong with it they answer that it is clean and well justified. We then ask whether the field is continuous across the interface, and they answer no. We ask whether it is differentiable, and they answer yes, since the derivation has just taken its divergence or its curl. The contradiction surfaces on its own, because they are now asserting that a function is differentiable but not continuous. As Idemen [9] shows, this is exactly the flaw in the standard argument. The divergence and Stokes theorems require the field to be smooth on the integration domain, and that hypothesis is precisely what fails at the interface. Once the difficulty is seen as a difficulty about the available mathematical language, the distributional derivation is no longer one method among others but the resolution of an inconsistency the students have just found for themselves. Beyond the technical flaw, the standard route leaves the physical origin of each condition implicit, so students carry conditions whose meaning is obscure when they later set up boundary value problems of their own.

We find it more natural to work with the electrostatic potential ϕ , related to \mathbf{E} by $\mathbf{E} = -\nabla\phi$. Both boundary conditions then emerge together from a single distributional equation, the Poisson equation for ϕ , and the conditions on \mathbf{E} follow by taking the gradient. Where the pillbox produces a condition and stops, the distributional Laplacian produces the condition and identifies the charge that causes it.

5.1 The Poisson equation in the sense of distributions

We begin our analysis by considering two volume domains Ω_1 and Ω_2 separated by a surface $S = \partial\Omega_1 \cap \partial\Omega_2$. Each domain is filled with some material, which in this work can be either a simple dielectric or an ideal ohmic conductor. Each domain may also contain an arbitrary charge distribution, whether volumetric, surface, line, or point, denoted $\rho_{\text{total},i}$ in Ω_i , $i = 1, 2$. In addition, charge distributions may exist on the boundary S itself. All charges, free and bound, are collectively denoted by ρ_{total} , and they characterize an electrostatic potential $\phi(\mathbf{x})$ that, due to the possible presence of charges on S , may be discontinuous across the interface. Because of this, it is necessary to consider the Poisson equation $\nabla^2\phi = -\epsilon_0^{-1}\rho_{\text{total}}$ in the sense of distributions. Using the formula for the Laplacian of a discontinuous function in Eq. (9), derived in Section 2, we have

$$\nabla^2\phi = \{\nabla^2\phi\} + \left[\left[\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial n} \right] \right] \delta_S + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{n} [[\phi]] \delta_S), \quad (35)$$

where \mathbf{n} is the unit normal vector to S , $\{\nabla^2\phi\}$ denotes the Laplacian without precaution, that is, the Laplacian applied within each domain Ω_i , $i = 1, 2$, $[[\phi]]$ is the jump of ϕ across S , and $[\partial_n\phi]$ is the jump of its normal derivative, both measured in the direction of \mathbf{n} .

The right-hand side of Eq. (35) must equal $-\epsilon_0^{-1}\rho_{\text{total}}$ in the sense of distributions. Matching the terms supported within each domain Ω_i on both sides, we obtain

$$\nabla^2\phi_i(\mathbf{x}) = -\epsilon_0^{-1}\rho_{\text{total},i}, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_i,$$

where $\phi_i = \phi|_{\Omega_i}$ is the restriction of the electrostatic potential to Ω_i .

The singular terms in Eq. (35) call for a physical interpretation, identified by computing the potential they generate. Applying the first singular term to $1/(4\pi\epsilon_0|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|)$, where the factor $-\epsilon_0$ arises from the $-\epsilon_0^{-1}$ multiplying ρ_{total} in the Poisson equation, yields

$$\left\langle -\epsilon_0 \left[\left[\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial n} \right] \right] \delta_S, \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right\rangle = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in S} \frac{-\epsilon_0 \left[\left[\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial n} \right] \right]}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} dS.$$

From this expression we see that $-\epsilon_0 \left[\left[\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial n} \right] \right] \delta_S$ must be interpreted as a surface density of monopoles, that is

$$-\epsilon_0 \left[\left[\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial n} \right] \right] \delta_S = \sigma_{\text{total}} \delta_S, \quad (36)$$

where $\sigma_{\text{total}} \delta_S$ is a surface charge distribution in the sense of Eq. (5). Using $\mathbf{E} = -\nabla\phi$, equation (36) can be expressed in terms of the normal component of the electrostatic field as,

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot [\mathbf{E}]|_S = \epsilon_0^{-1} \sigma_{\text{total}}|_S, \quad (37)$$

which is the standard result found in textbooks [1, 5] and tells us that the normal component of the electrostatic field may be discontinuous if there is a surface distribution of monopoles.

For the last term in Eq. (35), the same procedure, transferring the divergence onto the function $1/|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$ through the definition of the distributional derivative, yields

$$\left\langle -\epsilon_0 \nabla_{\mathbf{y}} \cdot (\mathbf{n} [[\phi]] \delta_S), \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0 |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right\rangle = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in S} \frac{\mathbf{n} \cdot (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) [[\phi]]}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|^3} dS. \quad (38)$$

Comparing with Eq. (30), we see that $-\epsilon_0 \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{n} [[\phi]] \delta_S)$ must be interpreted as a surface density of dipoles pointing in the direction of \mathbf{n} [19].

To determine the form of $[[\phi]]$, we consider Faraday's law interpreted in the sense of distributions, $\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = \vec{0}$. Using the formula for the curl of a discontinuous function in Eq. (8), this yields

$$\{\nabla \times \mathbf{E}\} + \mathbf{n} \times [[\mathbf{E}]]_S \delta_S = \vec{0},$$

and matching terms supported on S gives the boundary condition

$$\mathbf{n} \times [[\mathbf{E}]]_S = \vec{0},$$

that is, the tangential component of \mathbf{E} is continuous across S . To connect this with ϕ , we define the *tangential gradient* of a function f on S as its projection onto the surface:

$$\nabla_t f = \nabla f - (\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla f) \mathbf{n}.$$

Since ∇_t involves only derivatives tangential to S , it commutes with the jump operator $[[\cdot]]$ that measures the change along the normal direction, so that

$$[[\mathbf{E}_t]] = [[-\nabla_t \phi]] = -\nabla_t [[\phi]] = \vec{0}.$$

This implies that $[[\phi]]$ has zero tangential gradient on S , and therefore $[[\phi]]$ is at most a constant Φ_c on each connected component of S . We therefore write

$$-\epsilon_0 \nabla_{\mathbf{y}} \cdot (\mathbf{n} [[\phi(\mathbf{y})]]) \delta_S = -\epsilon_0 \nabla_{\mathbf{y}} \cdot (\mathbf{n} \Phi_c \delta_S),$$

where Φ_c is a constant on S . Physically, this means that the surface dipole layer, if present, must have uniform density across each connected component of S , consistent with the requirement that the tangential component of \mathbf{E} be continuous. Moreover, by making an analysis similar to the one for the point dipole case in Section 4, one can write

$$-\epsilon_0 \nabla_{\mathbf{y}} \cdot (\mathbf{n} \Phi_c \delta_S) = [-\epsilon_0 \Phi_c \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{y}}] \delta_S = \lim_{d \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\Phi_c \epsilon_0}{d} \delta_{S+dn} - \frac{\Phi_c \epsilon_0}{d} \delta_S \right],$$

where d is a distance measured in meters, $\frac{\Phi_c \epsilon_0}{d} \delta_S$ is a surface charge density on S , and $\frac{\Phi_c \epsilon_0}{d} \delta_{S+d\mathbf{n}}$ is a surface charge density on the surface obtained by translating each point of S by a vector $d\mathbf{n}$. This makes explicit the dipolar character of the surface distribution, constructed here as the limit of two surface charge densities of opposite sign brought together, the surface analogue of the point-dipole limit of Section 4 and the double layer of Vladimirov [19].

Summarizing our results, the total charge density ρ_{total} is explicitly given by

$$\rho_{\text{total}} = \rho_1|_{\Omega_1} + \rho_2|_{\Omega_2} + \sigma_{\text{total}}\delta_{S_1} + [-\epsilon_0\Phi_c\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla]\delta_{S_2},$$

where S_1 and S_2 are two surfaces such that $S_1 \cup S_2 = S$ and $S_1 \cap S_2 = \emptyset$. The reason for this partition is that the monopole density comes from the jump in the normal derivative of ϕ , while the dipole density comes from the jump in ϕ itself. Prescribing both on the same surface element would fix the potential and its normal derivative simultaneously, a Cauchy condition that overspecifies the boundary value problem [5]. A surface element of S therefore carries either a monopole density or a dipole density, but not both. The electrostatic potential generated by this charge configuration, measured at a position \mathbf{x} which is not located within the support of any source, is

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(\mathbf{x}) = & \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in \Omega_1} \frac{\rho_1(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} d^3\mathbf{y} + \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in \Omega_2} \frac{\rho_2(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} d^3\mathbf{y} \\ & + \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in S_1} \frac{\sigma_{\text{total}}(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} dS_1 + \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in S_2} \frac{\epsilon_0\Phi_c\mathbf{n} \cdot (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|^3} dS_2. \end{aligned}$$

In practice, however, this expression is not well suited for solving boundary value problems in the presence of material media. Instead, one solves the Poisson equation in each domain,

$$\nabla^2\phi_i(\mathbf{x}) = -\epsilon_0^{-1}\rho_{\text{total},i}, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_i, \quad (39)$$

supplemented by the boundary conditions

$$\left[\left[\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial n} \right] \right]_{S_1} = -\epsilon_0^{-1}\sigma_{\text{total}}|_{S_1}, \quad (40)$$

$$[[\phi]]_{S_2} = \Phi_c|_{S_2}. \quad (41)$$

5.1.1 Dielectric-dielectric interface We now consider the case where both domains are occupied by simple dielectrics with permittivities ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 respectively. In this case the constitutive relation in each domain is

$$\mathbf{D}_i = \epsilon_i\mathbf{E}_i = -\epsilon_i\nabla\phi_i, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_i, \quad i = 1, 2,$$

and the total charge density in each domain consists only of free charges, $\rho_{\text{total},i} = \rho_{f,i}$. Substituting into Eq. (39), the system of equations to be solved is

$$\nabla^2\phi_i = -\epsilon_i^{-1}\rho_{f,i}, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_i, \quad i = 1, 2,$$

supplemented by the boundary conditions at S . For a dielectric-dielectric interface, it is physically reasonable to assume that no dipole layer is present on S , so that $S_2 = \emptyset$ and $S_1 = S$. The boundary conditions (40)–(41) then reduce to

$$\begin{aligned} [[\phi]]_S &= 0, \\ \left(\epsilon_2 \frac{\partial\phi_2}{\partial n} - \epsilon_1 \frac{\partial\phi_1}{\partial n} \right)_S &= -\sigma_f|_S, \end{aligned}$$

where σ_f is the free surface charge density on S and \mathbf{n} points from Ω_1 to Ω_2 . In the absence of free surface charges ($\sigma_f = 0$), the second condition reduces to the continuity of the normal component of \mathbf{D} . These two conditions, which in standard references require pillbox arguments [1, 5], here emerge naturally from the distributional Poisson equation and the constitutive relations.

5.1.2 Dielectric-ohmic conductor interface We now consider the case where Ω_1 is occupied by a simple dielectric with permittivity ϵ_1 and Ω_2 by an ideal ohmic conductor with conductivity σ . The constitutive relations are

$$\mathbf{D}_1 = \epsilon_1\mathbf{E}_1 = -\epsilon_1\nabla\phi_1, \quad \mathbf{J}_2 = \sigma\mathbf{E}_2,$$

where \mathbf{J}_2 is the current density inside the conductor. In the electrostatic regime, charge distributions are stationary and therefore $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_2 = -\partial_t \rho = 0$. Combined with Ohm's law and $\nabla \times \mathbf{E}_2 = \mathbf{0}$, the Helmholtz decomposition theorem [6] implies

$$\mathbf{E}_2 = \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_2,$$

so that $\nabla \phi_2 = \mathbf{0}$ throughout Ω_2 and ϕ_2 is constant in Ω_2 . By the maximum principle for harmonic functions [28], this constant value is attained on the boundary S , giving

$$\phi_2|_S = \phi_c,$$

where ϕ_c is determined by the total charge on the conductor. The system of equations to be solved is therefore

$$\nabla^2 \phi_1 = -\epsilon_1^{-1} \rho_{f,1}, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_1,$$

supplemented by the boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1|_S &= \phi_c, \\ \epsilon_1 \frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial n} \Big|_S &= -\sigma_f|_S, \end{aligned}$$

where the first condition follows from $[[\phi]]_S = 0$ and $\phi_2|_S = \phi_c$, and the second from Eq. (40) with $\epsilon_2 \partial_n \phi_2 = 0$, with \mathbf{n} pointing from Ω_1 to Ω_2 . The free surface charge density σ_f is induced by the external field and is determined as part of the solution.

The boundary conditions derived in this section emerge naturally from the distributional Poisson equation and the constitutive relations of each medium, without invoking *ad hoc* geometric constructions such as the pillbox or the rectangular loop. This provides a unified framework applicable to any interface between two materials, where the resulting equations and their complexity depend strongly on the constitutive relations considered.

6 Classroom implementation

The material presented in this paper is taught as part of Electromagnetism II, a seventh-semester compulsory course in macroscopic electromagnetism whose official syllabus extends from electrostatics through covariant electrodynamics. We use the distributional framework throughout the course wherever the classical setting becomes strained, for instance current loops as one-dimensional distributions, dipole radiation, and discontinuities at material interfaces. The present paper addresses only the portion devoted to electrostatics in vacuum and in dielectrics, together with the boundary value problems at material interfaces. The application of distribution theory to the remaining parts of the course will be addressed in subsequent work.

The course is taken after Electromagnetism I and Advanced Mathematical Methods for Physics. Electromagnetism I is taught phenomenologically, typically following Griffiths [1], Purcell [3], or Reitz-Milford-Christy [20]. Students therefore arrive with strong physical intuition built on a phenomenological treatment, together with the heuristic manipulations of the Dirac delta that come with it, and without uniform prior exposure to distribution theory. The distributional tools used in this paper are therefore developed within Electromagnetism II itself, but not as a self-contained preliminary block. In our first two iterations of the course we presented the full mathematical machinery up front, and found that students did not see the physical applications of the mathematics until the very end, which left the formalism looking like an end in itself. In practice we now introduce each tool at the point in the course where its physical motivation arises. The structure of the present paper, where Section 2 groups the distributional machinery for ease of reference, should not be taken as a prescription for the order of classroom presentation.

The electrostatics covered in this paper is also where the vocabulary of the multipoles is first built, and that vocabulary carries far beyond it. The same point dipoles underlie the boundary conditions of Section 5, the derivation of the polarization vector from the microscopic Maxwell equations through spatial averaging [5], and, later in the course, dipole radiation in electrodynamics. None of these is the subject of the present paper, but each draws on the expressions and the language that the electrostatic multipole expansion introduces for the first time, which is why Section 4 is given the weight it carries here.

A defining feature of our practice is to use the distributional framework not only as a means of deriving new results, but as a diagnostic tool with which students can re-examine results they have already encountered in Electromagnetism I. We have found this use of the framework to be, in our experience, more valuable pedagogically than the rigour of the framework taken on its own. The

two diagnostic discussions reported in this paper, on the pillbox derivation of the boundary conditions in Section 5 and on the point dipole in Section 4, are characteristic of how the framework is used in class to turn a result the student had accepted on authority into one they can question and rebuild.

The cumulative effect of teaching this material within the distributional framework, as we have observed it over six semesters, has been a change in how students relate to the subject. Four aspects of this change stand out. First, students learn that an argument is not correct merely because it appears in a textbook or because the instructor presented it on the board. When they encounter the pillbox derivation and see, through the diagnostic discussion described above, that it relies on a hypothesis the very situation violates, they realise that the difficulties they had earlier attributed to their own lack of understanding were in fact real difficulties in the standard treatment. Second, the formalism makes the structure of the subject visible. Definitions, concepts and operations stop being conventions to be memorised and become consequences of a single mathematical framework, which the student can trace back when necessary. Third, the standard techniques of electrostatics are still part of the working vocabulary, but students now apply them knowing what each technique is meant to do and why it is the appropriate one for a given situation. Finally, with the selection of method no longer a matter of pattern matching, the student's attention is free to engage with the physics of the problem rather than with its mathematical machinery.

The change is visible in the kind of problems we are able to assign. Three examples from recent homework sets indicate the range. First, problems that ask the student to identify the charge distribution producing a given potential, for instance $\phi(\mathbf{x}) = C(1/r + 1/(2r_0)) \exp(-r/r_0)$, which require recognising that the singularity at the origin signals a point source whose magnitude is extracted by interpreting the Laplacian in the sense of distributions. Second, problems on the force and torque exerted between point multipoles of arbitrary order, derived directly from Eq. (26) and Eq. (28) for any combination of dipole, quadrupole, or higher orders. Third, problems that combine extended distributions with the operational equivalence between extended distributions and their point-multipole representatives, such as computing the force exerted on a point charge by a uniformly charged cube, or by a cube divided into octants of alternating sign. These last problems admit at least two distinct routes, namely a direct integration over the extended distribution and a reduction to the equivalent sum of point multipoles in the sense of Section 4.3. Both routes are accepted, and the choice of route, more than the final answer, is what the student is asked to make consciously.

We do not claim that this framework is appropriate for every upper-undergraduate electromagnetism course. It demands a higher level of mathematical maturity than a phenomenological treatment, and student reception varies. Those with stronger mathematical inclinations engage with it readily, while others perceive the formalism as an unnecessary detour from the physics. At our institution, students choose their section freely when enrolling, so the population that elects our course is self-selected toward acceptance of a mathematically demanding presentation, and whether the observations above extend to a course in which the framework is the only option remains an open question. For programs in which the methods course does not introduce distribution theory, an instructor wishing to adopt the framework must develop those tools within the electromagnetism course itself, an investment of class time that we have found to be repaid in the sequel.

7 Conclusions

The theory of distributions has long been recognized as the natural language for describing singular objects such as point charges and surface densities. Its systematic application to the standard problems of electrostatics, however, has remained largely absent from the pedagogical literature, and that is the gap the present work addresses.

We have shown that this framework does not merely restate known results with greater rigor. It makes their physical content more transparent, resolves conceptual ambiguities that persist in standard treatments, and yields results those treatments cannot reach. The electrostatic potential for an arbitrary charge distribution is derived directly from Maxwell's equations, without superposition or heuristic limits. The 2^n -pole point distributions emerge as explicit limiting configurations of point charges and as the natural building blocks of the multipole expansion. The monopole and dipole moments of an extended distribution reduce exactly to point objects, interpreted through the total charge and the centers of charge, while the quadrupole already carries a volumetric correction that the formalism locates precisely, the behavior at higher orders remaining an open question. The boundary conditions at material interfaces follow from a single distributional Poisson equation, without invoking pillbox or rectangular-loop arguments. Across all

three settings, a single mathematical framework yields, by a single procedure, what standard treatments handle by a patchwork of case-specific techniques.

The deeper lesson, we believe, is that the difficulties students encounter in electrostatics are not solely physical. They are also mathematical. Singular objects, such as point charges, are introduced without a rigorous framework, limits are taken without a topology, and boundary conditions are derived by arguments that contradict the theorems they invoke. The standard treatment, even at its most careful, acknowledges these difficulties without resolving them. The theory of distributions is not a mathematical ornament added on top of the physics. It carries a cost, the rigor and the mathematical maturity it demands, but in exchange it lets the physics be seen more clearly, and for the problems treated here that is a price worth paying.

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Author contributions

Both authors contributed equally to the conceptualization, mathematical development, pedagogical analysis, writing, and editing of this manuscript.

Data availability

No new data were created or analysed in this study.

Supplementary data

A self-contained introduction to the theory of distributions, including the construction of the function spaces, convergence notions, convolution and Fourier transforms in the distributional sense, and the proofs of the formulas used in the main text, is provided as Supplementary Material A.

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL A

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Supplementary Material A:

A self-contained introduction to the theory of distributions

(supplementary to the main paper “The theory of distributions in teaching electrostatics: Multipoles, forces, and boundary conditions”)

Abstract

This supplementary material provides a self-contained introduction to the theory of distributions developed by Laurent Schwartz, at the level used in the main paper. We construct the function spaces of test functions and Schwartz distributions, define the basic operations (derivative, translation, product with a smooth function, sequences and limits, Fourier transform, convolution), extend the formalism to several variables, introduce singular distributions supported on surfaces and curves, and derive the formulas for the gradient, divergence, curl, and Laplacian of a function with a jump discontinuity that are used in the boundary value problem section of the main text. Proofs are included. Readers who only need the operative results may consult the corresponding section of the main text, which collects them without proof.

S1 A crash course in the theory of distributions

The theory of distributions, developed by Laurent Schwartz in the 1950s, provides a rigorous mathematical framework that extends the classical notion of a function. This extension is particularly useful in physics, where objects such as point charges, impulsive forces, and idealized boundaries are routinely described by quantities that do not correspond to ordinary functions. In this section, we introduce the basic concepts of the theory of distributions that will be used throughout this work. Our presentation follows mainly the ideas in [1, 2]; the reader interested in a rigorous treatment is referred to [3–5].

The section is organized in two parts. The first part, Sections S1.1–S1.6, develops the theory in one spatial dimension. That is, we introduce the notion of test function space, define Schwartz distributions and their basic operations, and extend the Fourier transform to this distributional setting. The second part, Sections S1.7–S1.10, extends all of these constructions to \mathbb{R}^3 , introducing singular distributions supported on surfaces and curves, the distributional calculus of discontinuous functions across interfaces, and the Fourier transform of differential operators. These last tools are the ones directly applied in the derivations of Sections 3–5 of the main text.

S1.1 Function spaces and functionals

Before defining distributions, we need to specify the class of functions on which they will act. The idea is to choose a space of functions that is rich enough to encode the physical information we care about, yet small enough to ensure that all the operations we want to perform are well-defined. This motivates the following hierarchy of definitions.

A **function space** \mathcal{F} is a vector space whose elements are functions. The key property is that any linear combination of elements of \mathcal{F} remains in \mathcal{F} : if $\phi_1, \phi_2 \in \mathcal{F}$, then $\lambda_1\phi_1 + \lambda_2\phi_2 \in \mathcal{F}$ for all $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in \mathbb{C}$. A familiar example is the space of continuous functions on a given interval. Note that the set of functions with positive values is *not* a function space, since a linear combination with negative coefficients may leave this set.

We say that \mathcal{F} is a **topological function space** if a notion of convergence has been defined for its elements, that is, if we have given precise meaning to the expression $\phi_n \rightarrow \phi$. This notion of convergence will play a crucial role when we define distributions as continuous functionals.

A **functional** on \mathcal{F} is a mapping $T : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ that assigns a complex number to every function $\phi \in \mathcal{F}$. Following Schwartz’s notation, the number assigned by T to ϕ will be denoted $\langle T, \phi \rangle$. Three illustrative examples are:

- If \mathcal{F} is the space of integrable functions, then $\langle T, \phi \rangle = \int_{x \in \mathbb{R}} \phi(x) dx$ defines a functional.
- If \mathcal{F} is the space of differentiable functions, then $\langle T, \phi \rangle = \phi'(a)$ defines a functional.

- If \mathcal{F} is the space of continuous functions, then $\langle T, \phi \rangle = [\phi(0)]^2$ defines a functional; note, however, that this one is *not* linear.

A functional T is called **zero** (denoted $T = 0$) if $\langle T, \phi \rangle = 0$ for all $\phi \in \mathcal{F}$. It is called **linear** if for any $\phi_1, \phi_2 \in \mathcal{F}$ and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in \mathbb{C}$:

$$\langle T, \lambda_1 \phi_1 + \lambda_2 \phi_2 \rangle = \lambda_1 \langle T, \phi_1 \rangle + \lambda_2 \langle T, \phi_2 \rangle,$$

where it is understood that $\lambda_1 \phi_1 + \lambda_2 \phi_2 \in \mathcal{F}$. Finally, T is called **continuous** if for every sequence $\phi_n \rightarrow \phi$ in \mathcal{F} (in the chosen notion of convergence), the sequence of numbers $\langle T, \phi_n \rangle$ converges to $\langle T, \phi \rangle$.

S1.2 The space \mathcal{D} and Schwartz distributions

The natural function space for the theory of distributions is the space \mathcal{D} , defined as the vector space of C^∞ functions with compact support. Recall that the **support** of a function ϕ , denoted $\text{supp}(\phi)$, is the smallest closed set outside of which ϕ is identically zero. A canonical example of an element of \mathcal{D} is

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} \exp\left(\frac{-1}{1-|\mathbf{x}|^2}\right) & \text{if } |\mathbf{x}| < 1, \\ 0 & \text{if } |\mathbf{x}| \geq 1. \end{cases}$$

The space \mathcal{D} is topological under uniform convergence, making it suitable for defining continuous functionals. The elements of \mathcal{D} are called **test functions**.

Schwartz distributions are defined as the linear and continuous functionals on \mathcal{D} . The space of all such functionals, the topological dual of \mathcal{D} , is denoted \mathcal{D}' . Two distributions T_1 and T_2 are said to be **equal** if $\langle T_1 - T_2, \phi \rangle = 0$ for all $\phi \in \mathcal{D}$, that is, if they have the same effect on every test function.

It is worth emphasizing that distributions are defined on \mathcal{D} , but many of them can also act on functions outside \mathcal{D} . This is because numerous distributions arise as restrictions to \mathcal{D} of functionals defined on larger spaces. Petit [1], for instance, shows how physical quantities can be recovered as distributions acting on functions belonging to a space larger than \mathcal{D} , such as $\frac{1}{|\mathbf{x}|}$. We use this same idea to obtain the electrostatic potential, as the action of the charge distribution on the function $\frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{x}'|}$, which does not have compact support and is therefore not a test function. This construction is used throughout the present work.

S1.3 Regular and singular distributions

Not all distributions are equally exotic. A large and important class of distributions arises naturally from locally integrable functions. Recall that a function $f(x)$ is called **locally integrable** if it is integrable in the Lebesgue sense on every bounded subset of \mathbb{R}^3 [6]. To every locally integrable function f one can associate a distribution T_f defined by

$$\langle T_f, \phi \rangle = \int_{x \in \mathbb{R}} f(x) \phi(x) d^3 \mathbf{x}, \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}.$$

Making a common abuse of language, we say that locally integrable functions *are* distributions and write $\langle f, \phi \rangle = \int f \phi d^3 \mathbf{x}$ in place of $\langle T_f, \phi \rangle$. Distributions of this type are called **regular distributions**. Those that cannot be represented in this way are called **singular distributions**.

The most important example of a singular distribution is the **Dirac delta**, denoted δ and defined by

$$\langle \delta, \phi \rangle = \phi(0), \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}. \quad (\text{S1})$$

More generally, the **Dirac delta centered at a point** x_a is the distribution δ_{x_a} defined by

$$\langle \delta_{x_a}, \phi \rangle = \phi(x_a), \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}. \quad (\text{S2})$$

In physics it is customary to write $\delta(x)$ in place of δ and $\delta(x - x_a)$ in place of δ_{x_a} , and to use the integral notation [7]

$$\int_{x \in \mathbb{R}} \delta(x) \phi(x) dx = \phi(0), \quad \int_{x \in \mathbb{R}} \delta(x - x_a) \phi(x) dx = \phi(x_a).$$

We emphasize that these integral expressions are a convenient notation, not literal integrals: δ is not a locally integrable function and therefore cannot be integrated in the classical sense [8].

S1.4 Operations on distributions

One of the most powerful aspects of the theory of distributions is that many operations defined for smooth functions extend naturally to all distributions, including singular ones. The key principle behind each extension is the same. The definition adopted in the theory of distributions is the one that, on the regular distributions associated with smooth functions, agrees with the corresponding operation already well defined under the integral sign. In this section we introduce the operations in one dimension that will be used throughout this work.

S1.4.1 Linear combinations Since \mathcal{D}' is a vector space, linear combinations of distributions are defined in the natural way. If $T_1, T_2 \in \mathcal{D}'$ and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in \mathbb{C}$, then

$$\langle \lambda_1 T_1 + \lambda_2 T_2, \phi \rangle = \lambda_1 \langle T_1, \phi \rangle + \lambda_2 \langle T_2, \phi \rangle, \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}.$$

S1.4.2 Derivative of a distribution The extension of differentiation to distributions is motivated by the following observation. If f is a locally integrable function whose classical derivative f' is also locally integrable, then integration by parts gives

$$\langle T_{f'}, \phi \rangle = \int_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}} f'(\mathbf{x}) \phi(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} = - \int_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}} f(\mathbf{x}) \phi'(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} = - \langle T_f, \phi' \rangle,$$

where the boundary terms vanish because $\phi \in \mathcal{D}$ has compact support. This suggests the following general definition.

The derivative of a distribution $T \in \mathcal{D}'$ is the distribution T' defined by

$$\langle T', \phi \rangle = - \langle T, \phi' \rangle, \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}.$$

More generally, the m -th order derivative satisfies

$$\langle T^{(m)}, \phi \rangle = (-1)^m \langle T, \phi^{(m)} \rangle, \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}.$$

A remarkable consequence of this definition is that *every distribution is infinitely differentiable*. For example, the first two derivatives of the Dirac delta are

$$\langle \delta', \phi \rangle = -\phi'(0), \quad \langle \delta'', \phi \rangle = \phi''(0), \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}.$$

S1.4.3 Derivative of a discontinuous function A particularly important application of the distributional derivative arises when f is a locally integrable function that is differentiable everywhere except at a point $a \in \mathbb{R}$. At such a point, f may have a jump discontinuity. We define the **jump of f at a** as

$$[[f]](a) = f(a^+) - f(a^-),$$

where $f(a^\pm)$ denote the one-sided limits of f at a . A careful integration by parts then yields the following fundamental result:

$$f' = \{f'\} + [[f]](a) \delta_a, \tag{S3}$$

where $\{f'\}$ denotes the classical derivative of f applied where f is smooth, and $[[f]](a) \delta_a$ is the representation of the discontinuity at a . If f has finitely many discontinuities at points a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n , this generalizes to

$$f' = \{f'\} + \sum_{i=1}^n [[f]](a_i) \delta_{a_i}.$$

As a canonical example, the Heaviside function $H(\mathbf{x})$, defined as $H(x) = 1$ for $x \geq 0$ and $H(x) = 0$ for $x < 0$, satisfies $H' = \delta$ in the sense of distributions, since $[[H]](0) = 1$.

S1.4.4 Translation of a distribution If $f(x)$ is a locally integrable function, its translation by x_a is $f(x - x_a)$. A change of variables shows that

$$\int_{x \in \mathbb{R}} f(x - x_a) \phi(x) dx = \int_{x \in \mathbb{R}} f(\mathbf{x}) \phi(x + x_a) dx,$$

which motivates defining the **translation** of a distribution T by x_a as

$$\langle \tau_{x_a} T, \phi(x) \rangle = \langle T, \phi(x + x_a) \rangle, \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}.$$

For example, one can verify that $\tau_{x_a} \delta = \delta_{x_a}$, since

$$\langle \tau_{x_a} \delta, \phi(x) \rangle = \langle \delta, \phi(x + x_a) \rangle = \phi(0 + x_a) = \phi(x_a) = \langle \delta_{x_a}, \phi(x) \rangle.$$

S1.4.5 Leibniz rule If $\alpha(x)$ is a C^∞ function and T is a distribution, the product αT is the distribution defined by

$$\langle \alpha T, \phi \rangle = \langle T, \alpha \phi \rangle, \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}.$$

Note that $\alpha \phi \in \mathcal{D}$ since the product of a C^∞ function with a test function is again a test function. The **Leibniz rule** then states that

$$(\alpha T)' = \alpha' T + \alpha T',$$

which follows directly from the definitions and mirrors the classical product rule for derivatives.

S1.5 Sequences of distributions and the Dirac delta as a limit

Just as functions can be approximated by sequences of simpler functions, distributions can be approximated by sequences of regular distributions. This is particularly useful for giving rigorous meaning to the physicist's intuitive representations; for instance, understanding the Dirac delta as the limit of a family of increasingly concentrated but normalized functions. The following definition makes this notion of convergence precise.

A sequence of distributions T_α is said to **converge** to a distribution T as $\alpha \rightarrow \lambda$ if

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow \lambda} \langle T_\alpha, \phi \rangle = \langle T, \phi \rangle, \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}.$$

A classical example is the family of functions

$$f_\alpha(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\alpha} & \text{if } 0 \leq x \leq \alpha, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

which defines a family of regular distributions T_{f_α} . As $\alpha \rightarrow 0$, since ϕ is continuous,

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} \langle T_{f_\alpha}, \phi \rangle = \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\alpha} \int_0^\alpha \phi(x) dx = \phi(0) = \langle \delta, \phi \rangle,$$

so $T_{f_\alpha} \rightarrow \delta$ in the sense of distributions. This provides a rigorous justification for the physicist's intuition of the Dirac delta as a function that takes *very large values on very small intervals*. In electrostatics, this limit corresponds to the idealization of a point charge as the limit of an increasingly concentrated volumetric charge distribution.

S1.6 The Fourier transform in the sense of distributions

The Fourier transform is one of the central tools for solving partial differential equations in physics. Its key virtue is that it converts differentiation into multiplication, turning the Poisson equation into an algebraic equation in Fourier space. To apply this tool to the distributions already defined, which can be singular, it is necessary to consider the Fourier transform in the sense of distributions.

S1.6.1 The Schwartz space \mathcal{S} To extend the Fourier transform to distributions, we need a function space whose elements are well behaved under the Fourier transform. The space \mathcal{D} is not suitable for this purpose, since the Fourier transform of a compactly supported function generally does not have compact support. Instead, we work with the **Schwartz space \mathcal{S}** , defined as the vector space of C^∞ functions $\phi: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ such that

- (a) All derivatives $\phi^{(m)}(x)$ exist for every $m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.
- (b) For any integers m and p (positive, negative, or zero), the product $x^p \phi^{(m)}(x)$ is bounded.

Informally, $\phi \in \mathcal{S}$ if ϕ and all its derivatives decay to zero faster than any power of $1/|x|$ as $|x| \rightarrow \infty$ [9]. Under this definition, \mathcal{D} is a subspace of \mathcal{S} .

The **tempered distributions** are defined as the linear and continuous functionals on \mathcal{S} , and their space is denoted \mathcal{S}' . Since $\mathcal{D} \subset \mathcal{S}$, every tempered distribution restricts to a Schwartz distribution.

S1.6.2 The Fourier transform The **Fourier transform** of a tempered distribution $T \in \mathcal{S}'$ is the distribution $\hat{T} = \mathcal{F}\{T\} \in \mathcal{S}'$ defined by [9, 10]

$$\langle \mathcal{F}\{T\}, \phi \rangle = \langle T, \mathcal{F}\{\phi\} \rangle, \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{S},$$

where, in this work, $\mathcal{F}\{\phi\}(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{k \in \mathbb{R}} \phi(k) e^{+ikx} dk$ is the classical Fourier transform of the test function. Making the variables explicit:

$$\langle \hat{T}(k), \phi(k) \rangle = \langle T(x), \hat{\phi}(x) \rangle.$$

The inverse Fourier transform is defined analogously. As a paradigmatic example, let us consider the **Fourier transform of δ** . Using the definition,

$$\langle \mathcal{F}_{x \rightarrow k}\{\delta\}, \phi(k) \rangle = \langle \delta(x), \hat{\phi}(x) \rangle = \hat{\phi}(0) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{k \in \mathbb{R}} \phi(k) dk = \left\langle \frac{1}{2\pi}, \phi(k) \right\rangle,$$

so $\mathcal{F}_{x \rightarrow k}\{\delta(x)\} = \frac{1}{2\pi}$. Conversely, $\mathcal{F}_{k \rightarrow x}^{-1}\{\delta(k)\} = 1$. Another well known result that must be extended in the sense of distribution is the Fourier transform of T' , that is

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathcal{F}_{x \rightarrow k}\{T'(x)\}, \phi(k) \rangle &= \langle T'(x), \hat{\phi}(x) \rangle, \\ &= - \langle T(x), \hat{\phi}'(x) \rangle, \\ &= - \langle T(x), \mathcal{F}_{k \rightarrow x}\{ik\phi(k)\} \rangle, \\ &= - \langle \mathcal{F}_{x \rightarrow k}\{T(x)\}, ik\phi(k) \rangle, \\ &= \langle -ik\hat{T}(k), \phi(k) \rangle. \end{aligned} \tag{S4}$$

Thus, we have recovered one of the characteristic properties of classical Fourier transform. This result will be used in Subsection [S1.10](#) to prove the theorem on differential operators.

S1.7 Distributions in several variables

The one-dimensional theory developed in the previous sections extends straightforwardly to \mathbb{R}^3 . The key step is to replace the space \mathcal{D} of smooth compactly supported functions of one variable by its three-dimensional analogue $\mathcal{D}^{(3)}$, and to define distributions as continuous linear functionals on this new space. Throughout the remainder of this work, $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ unless otherwise stated, and we use the notation $T(\mathbf{x})$ to indicate that T acts on test functions of three variables.

For a locally integrable function $f(\mathbf{x})$, the associated regular distribution is

$$\langle T_f, \phi \rangle = \int_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3} f(\mathbf{x}) \phi(\mathbf{x}) d^3\mathbf{x}, \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}^{(3)}.$$

The Dirac delta distribution $\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_a)$ is defined by

$$\langle \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_a), \phi(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \phi(\mathbf{x}_a), \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}^{(3)}.$$

S1.8 Singular distributions

In three dimensions, charge distributions need not be volumetric. Surface charges, line charges, and point charges are physically meaningful, yet they assign charge to sets of measure zero in \mathbb{R}^3 and therefore cannot be described by locally integrable functions. Within this framework, all of these cases are handled uniformly: One simply replaces the volume integral in the definition of a regular distribution by the appropriate operation; that is a lower-dimensional integral for surface and line charges, or an evaluation at a point for point charges.

In the context of electrostatics, the Dirac delta provides the natural mathematical model for a point charge. A point charge of magnitude q localized at position \mathbf{x}_0 is described by the charge density [11, 12]

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}) = q \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0).$$

If $S \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ is a surface and $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$ is a function defined on S , the distribution $\sigma\delta_S$ is defined by [1]

$$\langle \sigma\delta_S, \phi \rangle = \int_{\mathbf{x} \in S} \sigma(\mathbf{x}) \phi(\mathbf{x}) dS, \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}^{(3)}. \tag{S5}$$

Analogously, if \mathcal{C} is a curve and $\lambda(\mathbf{x})$ is a function defined on \mathcal{C} , the distribution $\lambda\delta_{\mathcal{C}}$ is defined by

$$\langle \lambda\delta_{\mathcal{C}}, \phi \rangle = \int_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{C}} \lambda(\mathbf{x})\phi(\mathbf{x}) dC, \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}^{(3)}.$$

In this way, volumetric, surface, line, and point charge distributions are all instances of the same mathematical object, a distribution, differing only in the dimension of their support.

S1.9 Operations on distributions in several variables

We now extend the operational calculus of distributions to \mathbb{R}^3 . The definitions of partial derivatives, tensor products, and change of variables follow the same principle as in one dimension. Each is adopted so as to agree, on the regular distributions associated with smooth functions, with the corresponding operation already well defined under the integral sign, and the resulting form is then taken as the definition for all distributions. The most important new result is the distributional derivative of a function that is discontinuous across a surface. This result is not simply the classical differential operator applied piecewise, but acquires additional singular terms supported on the discontinuity surface. These singular terms carry the physical information about surface charges and interface conditions, and they are what makes the distributional Poisson equation yield the boundary conditions of Section 5.

S1.9.1 Derivatives in the sense of distributions in \mathbb{R}^3 The **partial derivatives** of a distribution $T(\mathbf{x})$ are defined by [5]

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i}, \phi \right\rangle = (-1) \left\langle T, \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_i} \right\rangle, \quad i = 1, 2, 3,$$

and more generally

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}, \phi \right\rangle = \left\langle T, \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} \right\rangle, \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3.$$

As in the one-dimensional case, every distribution in \mathbb{R}^3 is infinitely differentiable in this sense.

The one-dimensional jump formula (S3) extends to three dimensions in a natural way. Let $f(\mathbf{x}) = f(x_1, x_2, x_3)$ be a locally integrable function, differentiable in the complement of a surface $S \subset \mathbb{R}^3$. Then its distributional partial derivatives are given by [1]

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i} = \left\{ \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i} \right\} + n_i [[f]] \delta_S, \quad i = 1, 2, 3,$$

where $\mathbf{n} = (n_1, n_2, n_3)$ is the unit normal to S and $[[f]]$ is the jump of f across S . From this, the following four fundamental formulas follow [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla f &= \{\nabla f\} + \mathbf{n} [[f]] \delta_S, \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{F} &= \{\nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}\} + \mathbf{n} \cdot [[\mathbf{F}]] \delta_S, \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{F} &= \{\nabla \times \mathbf{F}\} + \mathbf{n} \times [[\mathbf{F}]] \delta_S, \end{aligned} \tag{S6}$$

$$\nabla^2 f = \{\nabla^2 f\} + \left[\left[\frac{\partial f}{\partial n} \right] \right] \delta_S + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{n} [[f]] \delta_S), \tag{S7}$$

where $[[\mathbf{F}]]$ denotes the jump of the vector field \mathbf{F} across S and $\partial f / \partial n = \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla f$ is the normal derivative. These four formulas are central to the treatment of boundary value problems in electrostatics, as will become apparent in the following sections.

S1.9.2 Tensor product of distributions If $f(x)$ and $g(y)$ are locally integrable functions of a single variable, their product $p(x, y) = f(x)g(y)$ is locally integrable in \mathbb{R}^2 . This observation motivates the following definition.

Given two distributions $T(x) \in \mathcal{D}'_x$ and $S(y) \in \mathcal{D}'_y$, their **tensor product** $T(x)S(y)$ is the distribution on $\mathcal{D}^{(2)}$ defined by

$$\langle T(x)S(y), \phi(x, y) \rangle = \langle T(x), \langle S(y), \phi(x, y) \rangle \rangle, \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}^{(2)}.$$

Two important theorems, which we state without proof [3], guarantee that this definition is well-posed:

Theorem 1. (Derivative under the distribution sign) If $\phi(x, y) \in \mathcal{D}^{(2)}$, then the function $\psi(y) = \langle T(x), \phi(x, y) \rangle$ belongs to \mathcal{D} regardless of the choice of $T(x)$. Moreover, ψ is C^∞ and $\frac{d\psi}{dy} = \left\langle T(x), \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} \right\rangle$.

Theorem 2 (Fubini for distributions). If $T(x) \in \mathcal{D}'_x$ and $S(y) \in \mathcal{D}'_y$, then

$$\langle T(x)S(y), \phi(x, y) \rangle = \langle S(y), \langle T(x), \phi(x, y) \rangle \rangle. \quad (\text{S8})$$

This result is often called the *Fubini theorem for distributions* and allows us to interchange the order of action of two distributions, in direct analogy with the classical Fubini theorem for integrals.

As a concrete example, one can verify that $\delta(x)\delta(y)\delta(z) = \delta(\mathbf{x})$, since

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \delta(x)\delta(y)\delta(z), \phi(x, y, z) \rangle &= \langle \delta(x), \langle \delta(y), \langle \delta(z), \phi(x, y, z) \rangle \rangle \rangle \\ &= \langle \delta(x), \langle \delta(y), \phi(x, y, 0) \rangle \rangle \\ &= \langle \delta(x), \phi(x, 0, 0) \rangle \\ &= \phi(0, 0, 0) = \langle \delta(\mathbf{x}), \phi(x, y, z) \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

S1.9.3 Change of variables Let $\Omega' \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ be open sets and $\mathbb{F} : \Omega' \rightarrow \Omega$ a diffeomorphism. For a locally integrable function f , a change of variables gives

$$\int_{\Omega'} f(\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{r}))\phi(\mathbf{r}) d^3\mathbf{r} = \int_{\Omega} f(\mathbf{x})\phi(\mathbb{F}^{-1}(\mathbf{x})) |\det \text{Jac}(\mathbb{F}^{-1})(\mathbf{x})| d^3\mathbf{x},$$

which motivates defining the **change of variables** for a distribution T as

$$\langle T \circ \mathbb{F}, \phi \rangle = \langle T, \phi \circ (\mathbb{F}^{-1}) |\det \text{Jac}(\mathbb{F}^{-1})| \rangle.$$

An important application is the expression of the Dirac delta in curvilinear coordinates. In spherical coordinates, where $\mathbb{F}(r, \theta, \varphi) = (r \cos \varphi \sin \theta, r \sin \varphi \sin \theta, r \cos \theta)$, one obtains

$$\delta(x - x_0)\delta(y - y_0)\delta(z - z_0) = \frac{\delta(r - r_0)\delta(\theta - \theta_0)\delta(\varphi - \varphi_0)}{r^2 \sin \theta},$$

and analogously in cylindrical coordinates

$$\delta(x - x_0)\delta(y - y_0)\delta(z - z_0) = \frac{\delta(\rho - \rho_0)\delta(\theta - \theta_0)\delta(z - z_0)}{\rho}.$$

S1.10 The Fourier transform of differential operators

The Fourier transform is the central tool for solving the differential equations that model electrostatic phenomena. It converts differential operators into algebraic ones, separating the information of the source from that of the operator, and the convolution theorem tells us how to recover the solution in physical space. Since charge distributions are not necessarily volumetric, all of these results must be understood in the sense of distributions.

S1.10.1 The Fourier transform in \mathbb{R}^3 The Schwartz space \mathcal{S} and the tempered distributions \mathcal{S}' introduced in Section S1.6 extend without modification to \mathbb{R}^3 : One simply requires that $\phi : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is C^∞ and that for every integer N and multi-index α , the product $\|\mathbf{x}\|^N \phi^{(\alpha)}(\mathbf{x})$ remains bounded as $\|\mathbf{x}\| \rightarrow \infty$ [5].

Mirroring the case in one dimension, the **Fourier transform** of a tempered distribution $T \in \mathcal{S}'$ is the distribution $\hat{T} = \mathcal{F}\{T\} \in \mathcal{S}'$ defined by

$$\langle \mathcal{F}\{T\}, \phi \rangle = \langle T, \mathcal{F}\{\phi\} \rangle, \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{S},$$

with the convention $\mathcal{F}\{\phi\}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \phi(\mathbf{k}) e^{+i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}} d^3\mathbf{k}$ as the classical Fourier transform of the test function. Making the variables explicit:

$$\langle \hat{T}(\mathbf{x}), \phi(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \langle T(\mathbf{k}), \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{k}) \rangle.$$

The inverse Fourier transform is defined analogously. Due to its importance in representing a point charge distribution, let us consider the **Fourier transform of δ** . Using the definition,

$$\langle \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{k}}\{\delta\}, \phi(\mathbf{k}) \rangle = \langle \delta(\mathbf{x}), \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{0}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \phi(\mathbf{k}) d^3\mathbf{k} = \left\langle \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3}, \phi(\mathbf{k}) \right\rangle, \quad (\text{S9})$$

so $\mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{k}}\{\delta(\mathbf{x})\} = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3}$. Conversely, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{x}}^{-1}\{\delta(\mathbf{k})\} = 1$.

S1.10.2 Fourier transform of differential operators The following theorem summarizes the action of the Fourier transform on the differential operators that appear in Maxwell's equations.

Theorem. Let $f(\mathbf{x})$ and $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})$ be scalar and vector tempered distributions respectively. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i)} \quad & \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{k}} \{ \nabla f(\mathbf{x}) \} = -i\mathbf{k} \tilde{f}(\mathbf{k}), \\ \text{ii)} \quad & \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{k}} \{ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) \} = -i\mathbf{k} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{F}}(\mathbf{k}), \\ \text{iii)} \quad & \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{k}} \{ \nabla^2 f(\mathbf{x}) \} = -(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{k}) \tilde{f}(\mathbf{k}), \\ \text{iv)} \quad & \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{k}} \{ \nabla \times \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) \} = -i\mathbf{k} \times \tilde{\mathbf{F}}(\mathbf{k}), \end{aligned} \tag{S10}$$

where $\tilde{f}(\mathbf{k}) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{k}} \{ f(\mathbf{x}) \}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{F}}(\mathbf{k}) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{k}} \{ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) \}$. The proof follows directly from (S4) and the definition of the Fourier transform; see [2] for details.

S1.10.3 Convolution of distributions For two locally integrable functions f and g on \mathbb{R}^3 , and following our convention of Fourier transform, we define the operation of classical convolution as:

$$(f * g)(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3} f(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) g(\mathbf{y}) d^3\mathbf{y}.$$

This operation can be extended in the sense of distributions as follows: Consider the distributions $T(\mathbf{x})$, $S(\mathbf{x})$, at least one of which has compact support, their **convolution** $T * S$ is defined by [1]

$$\langle (T * S)(\mathbf{x}), \phi(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \langle T(\mathbf{x}) S(\mathbf{y}), \phi(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y}) \rangle, \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{D}. \tag{S11}$$

The **convolution theorem** then states that for $T, S \in \mathcal{S}'$,

$$\mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{k}} \{ (T * S)(\mathbf{x}) \} = \tilde{T}(\mathbf{k}) \tilde{S}(\mathbf{k}). \tag{S12}$$

Although the tools of distribution theory introduced in this section may seem abstract compared to standard calculus, they form a coherent and unified language in which every charge distribution, whether volumetric, surface, line, or point, is treated on equal footing, and in which the classical results of electrostatics emerge not from *ad hoc* manipulations, but as natural consequences of a single mathematical framework. The following sections put these tools to work, revisiting several concepts in electrostatics.

S2 Detailed derivations from Section 4 of the main text

S2.1 Convolution for a one-dimensional charge distribution

In Section 3 of the main text, the electrostatic potential of a non-volumetric charge density is obtained by taking the convolution in the sense of distributions, Eq. (S11). We give here the detailed calculation for the one-dimensional charge distribution $\rho_\lambda(\mathbf{x}) = \lambda(\mathbf{x})\delta_C$, where C is a curve in space and λ is a charge linear density defined on C , with units of coulomb per meter. The electrostatic potential $\phi_\lambda(\mathbf{x})$ is given by

$$\phi_\lambda(\mathbf{x}) = (G * \lambda\delta_C)(\mathbf{x}).$$

Explicitly in the sense of distributions,

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \phi_\lambda(\mathbf{x}), \varphi(\mathbf{x}) \rangle &= \langle (G * \lambda \delta_C)(\mathbf{x}), \varphi(\mathbf{x}) \rangle \\
&= \left\langle \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} G(\mathbf{z}) \lambda(\mathbf{y}) \delta_C, \varphi(\mathbf{z} + \mathbf{y}) \right\rangle \\
&= \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \left\langle \frac{1}{|\mathbf{z}|}, \langle \lambda(\mathbf{y}) \delta_C, \varphi(\mathbf{z} + \mathbf{y}) \rangle \right\rangle \quad \text{plugging Eq.(??)} \\
&= \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \left\langle \frac{1}{|\mathbf{z}|}, \int_{\mathbf{y} \in C} \lambda(\mathbf{y}) \varphi(\mathbf{z} + \mathbf{y}) dC \right\rangle \quad \text{by definition of } \lambda \delta_C \\
&= \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int_{\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in C} \frac{\lambda(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{z}|} \varphi(\mathbf{z} + \mathbf{y}) dC d^3 \mathbf{z} \quad \text{by definition of regular distribution} \\
&= \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in C} \frac{\lambda(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \varphi(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{y} d^3 \mathbf{x} \quad \text{by making } \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z} \\
&= \int_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in C} \frac{\lambda(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} dC \varphi(\mathbf{x}) d^3 \mathbf{x} \\
&= \left\langle \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in C} \frac{\lambda(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} dC, \varphi(\mathbf{x}) \right\rangle \quad \text{by definition of regular distribution.}
\end{aligned}$$

Thus we can write

$$\phi_\lambda(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in C} \frac{\lambda(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} dC,$$

which is found in many textbooks as [13, 14].

S2.2 Inductive proof of the Taylor expansion of the Dirac delta

This section provides the inductive proof of the identity used in the construction of point multipoles (Sec. 4 of the main text). The approach follows Raimond [15] and Scharf [16].

Starting from

$$\langle \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_1), \varphi(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \langle \delta(\mathbf{x}), \varphi(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x}_1) \rangle = \varphi(\mathbf{x}_1),$$

and expanding $\varphi(\mathbf{x}_1)$ in a Taylor series around the origin yields

$$\varphi(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{[\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^n}{n!} \varphi(\mathbf{x}) + \frac{[\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^{N+1}}{(N+1)!} \varphi(\xi \mathbf{x}_1), \quad \xi \in [0, 1].$$

To express this as the action of an unknown distribution on $\varphi(\mathbf{x})$, we determine the distribution by analyzing each term. The case $n = 0$ is

$$\varphi(\mathbf{0}) = \langle \delta(\mathbf{x}), \varphi(\mathbf{x}) \rangle.$$

The case $n = 1$ uses the fact that $[\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla] \varphi(\mathbf{x})$ is also a test function:

$$\begin{aligned}
[\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla] \varphi(\mathbf{0}) &= \langle \delta(\mathbf{x}), [\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla] \varphi(\mathbf{x}) \rangle, \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^3 \left\langle \delta(\mathbf{x}), x_{1i} \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x_i}(\mathbf{x}) \right\rangle, \\
&= - \sum_{i=1}^3 \left\langle x_{1i} \frac{\partial \delta}{\partial x_i}(\mathbf{x}), \varphi(\mathbf{x}) \right\rangle, \\
&= \langle [-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla] \delta(\mathbf{x}), \varphi(\mathbf{x}) \rangle.
\end{aligned}$$

With the cases $n = 0, 1$ established, we formulate the inductive hypothesis:

$$\frac{[\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^n \varphi(\mathbf{0})}{n!} = \left\langle \frac{[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^n \delta(\mathbf{x})}{n!}, \varphi(\mathbf{x}) \right\rangle.$$

The inductive step is straightforward:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{[\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^{n+1} \varphi(\mathbf{0})}{(n+1)!} &= \frac{[\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^n}{(n)!} \left(\frac{[\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla] \varphi(\mathbf{x})}{n+1} \right), \\ &= \left\langle \frac{[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^n \delta(\mathbf{x})}{n!}, \frac{[\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla] \varphi(\mathbf{x})}{n+1} \right\rangle, \\ &= \left\langle \frac{[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^{n+1} \delta(\mathbf{x})}{(n+1)!}, \varphi(\mathbf{x}) \right\rangle, \end{aligned}$$

which completes the inductive proof. A similar manipulation gives the Lagrange remainder as

$$\frac{[\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^{N+1}}{(N+1)!} \varphi(\xi \mathbf{x}_1) = \left\langle \frac{[-\mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \nabla]^{N+1} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \xi \mathbf{x}_1)}{(N+1)!}, \varphi(\mathbf{x}) \right\rangle.$$

The Taylor expansion of $\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_1)$ in the sense of distributions follows by reading off the operator that acts on φ in each term.

S2.3 Change of variables in the quadrupole extended contribution

In Section 4 of the main text, the change of variables $\mathbf{y} = (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) + \mathbf{x}^\pm$ applied to

$$\phi_2^\pm(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x}|^3} \int_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3} \rho^\pm(\mathbf{y}) (3(\mathbf{y} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}})^2 - |\mathbf{y}|^2) d^3\mathbf{y}$$

splits the integrand into a contribution that depends on \mathbf{x}^\pm alone (yielding $\phi_{2,\text{point}}^\pm$) and a contribution that depends on $\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm$ (yielding $\phi_{2,\text{extended}}^\pm$). The cross terms vanish upon integration because \mathbf{x}^\pm is the centroid of ρ^\pm , so that $\int (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) \rho^\pm d^3\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{0}$.

To analyze $\phi_{2,\text{extended}}^\pm$, introduce spherical coordinates centered at \mathbf{x}^\pm :

$$\begin{aligned} y_1 - x_1^\pm &= r \sin \vartheta \cos \varphi, \\ y_2 - x_2^\pm &= r \sin \vartheta \sin \varphi, \\ y_3 - x_3^\pm &= r \cos \vartheta, \end{aligned}$$

with ϑ the angle between $\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm$ and $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$. The integrand $3((\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}})^2 - |\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm|^2$ then equals $2r^2 P_2(\cos \vartheta)$, where $P_2(\cos \vartheta) = (3 \cos^2 \vartheta - 1)/2$ is the Legendre polynomial of degree 2. Hence

$$\phi_{2,\text{extended}}^\pm(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Q^\pm}{|\mathbf{x}|^3} \int_0^R \int_0^\pi \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\rho^\pm(r, \vartheta, \varphi)}{Q^\pm} P_2(\cos \vartheta) r^2 \sin \vartheta d\varphi d\vartheta dr,$$

where R is the radius of the support of ρ^\pm measured from \mathbf{x}^\pm . Denoting the integral by $C^\pm/2$, this gives the form $\phi_{2,\text{extended}}^\pm = Q^\pm C^\pm / (4\pi\epsilon_0 |\mathbf{x}|^3)$ used in the main text.

S2.4 Vector form of the quadrupole extended contribution

The integrand of $\phi_{2,\text{extended}}^\pm$ in vector form is

$$3((\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}})^2 - |\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm|^2.$$

Writing the second term as the sum of its parallel and perpendicular components with respect to $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$,

$$|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm|^2 = |\hat{\mathbf{n}}((\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}})|^2 + |(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) - \hat{\mathbf{n}}((\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}})|^2,$$

and using $((\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}})^2 = |\hat{\mathbf{n}}((\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}})|^2$, the integrand decomposes as

$$2|\hat{\mathbf{n}}((\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}})|^2 - |(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) - \hat{\mathbf{n}}((\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}^\pm) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}})|^2.$$

Each term integrates to a moment of inertia of ρ^\pm/Q^\pm about the axis $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ and the plane perpendicular to $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$, respectively, with radii of gyration centered at \mathbf{x}^\pm . Combining $\phi_{2,\text{point}}^\pm$ and $\phi_{2,\text{extended}}^\pm$ then yields equation (34).

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